

Linking Research & Innovation for Gender Equality

D4.1 Evaluation methodology

WP4 – Monitoring and evaluation

Version: 1.0

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Executive summary

The present document, elaborated in collaboration with the experts of FUOC¹ (Foundation Open University of Catalonia), results from work carried out under T4.1 Evaluation methodology. As such, it comprises two broad sections which correspond to the methodology for the “formative evaluation” and the “summative evaluation”².

As described under Task 4.2 of the work package description in the Grant Agreement, the formative evaluation will enable implementing institutions to assess and monitor the progress of their GEP implementation. It takes place during the project’s lifetime with the aim of improving and steering the structural change process. Aligned from the outset with the GEP design, it is inherently a self-evaluation, carried out by each of the GEP working groups. As a consequence, the corresponding methodological framework has the purpose to familiarize partners with the basic steps of designing and implementing a formative evaluation as they design and implement their respective Gender Equality Plans. It will not specify detailed research questions or indicators as these need to be developed by each implementing partner in accordance with their context specific GEP objectives and actions.

On the other hand, the “summative evaluation” as described under Task 4.3 of the work package description will be carried out towards the end of the project by an external, independent evaluator. It will assess the short-term, and medium-term outcomes as well as the long-term impact of the GEP implementation in each of the 9 RPO/RFOs. The corresponding methodological framework specifies the evaluation design itself, including detailed accounts of data collection methods, research questions, measurement instruments and indicators to be used.

¹ FOUC was subcontracted by Smart Venice in order to elaborate the Evaluation methodology within WP4, in line with what was foreseen in the GA, namely that a qualified external entity would be identified for supporting the development of T4.1 and its related deliverable.

² The official D4.1 title as per the GA is “Formative Evaluation Methodology” is due to a typo in the proposal preparation phase. This is confirmed also by the Deliverable description itself also broadly formulated: “this report will present the methodology, indicators and targets for monitoring and assessing the GEPs implementation” (CALIPER Grant Agreement, pag. 21. Also, Task 4.1 description from whom this report stems, description refers to both formative and summative evaluation.

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Glossary

Activity

Actions taken or work performed through which inputs, such as funds, technical assistance and other types of resources are mobilized to produce specific outputs. (OECD 2002)

Assumption

Hypotheses about factors or risks which could affect the progress or success of a development intervention. Note: Assumptions can also be understood as hypothesized conditions that bear on the validity of the evaluation itself, e.g., about the characteristics of the population when designing a sampling procedure for a survey. Assumptions are made explicit in theory-based evaluations where evaluation tracks systematically the anticipated results chain. (OECD 2002)

Attribution

The ascription of a causal link between observed (or expected to be observed) changes and a specific intervention. Note: Attribution refers to that which is to be credited for the observed changes or results achieved. It represents the extent to which observed development effects can be attributed to a specific intervention or to the performance of one or more partner(s) taking into account other interventions, (anticipated or unanticipated) confounding factors, or external shocks. (OECD 2002)

Complexity

In complex systems, multiple parts interact in such a way that precise prediction is not possible. Complex systems are non-deterministic, meaning they cannot be reduced to their parts or simple rules of interaction among the parts. Interacting parts of a complex system create an emergent order that cannot be reduced to its constituent elements (Byrne and Callaghan 2013).

Contribution

Contribution analysis provides rigor in thinking critically about the relationship between central actors and activities and other influences within a complex multi-actor environment. It also facilitates a more purposeful, deeper, and systematic consideration of the myriad potential influences on policy outcomes. (Centre for Evaluation Innovation)

Critical Friend

The term critical friend describes a stance an evaluator can take in his or her relationship with the program or project they evaluate. Costa and Kallick (1993) provide this seminal definition: "A trusted person who asks provocative questions, provides data to be examined through another lens, and offers critique of a person's work as a friend" (p.50). (Evaluate)

Feminist Evaluation

Feminist evaluation (FE) emphasises participatory, empowering, and social justice agendas. Unlike most gender approaches, feminist evaluation does not provide a framework or advocate a precise approach; feminist evaluation is instead often defined as a way of thinking about evaluation. (Better Evaluation Framework)

Formative Evaluation

Evaluation intended to improve performance, most often conducted during the implementation phase of projects or programs. Note: Formative evaluations may also be conducted for other reasons such as compliance, legal requirements or as part of a larger evaluation initiative. (OECD 2002)

Independent Evaluation

An evaluation carried out by entities and persons free of the control of those responsible for the design and implementation of the development intervention. Note: The credibility of an evaluation depends in part on how

independently it has been carried out. Independence implies freedom from political influence and organizational pressure. It is characterized by full access to information and by full autonomy in carrying out investigations and reporting findings. (OECD 2002)

Indicator

Quantitative or qualitative factor or variable that provides a simple and reliable means to measure achievement, to reflect the changes connected to an intervention, or to help assess the performance of a development actor (OECD 2002).

Input

Input: Human, financial or other resource used to produce an output. (UNESCO (2007) Evaluation Handbook)

Impact

Positive and negative, primary and secondary long-term effects produced by a development intervention, directly or indirectly, intended or unintended. (OECD 2002)

Logical Framework (log frame)

Management tool used to improve the design of interventions, most often at the project level. It involves identifying strategic elements (inputs, outputs, outcomes, impact) and their causal relationships, indicators, and the assumptions or risks that may influence success and failure. It thus facilitates planning, execution and evaluation of a development intervention. (OECD 2002).

Quadruple Helix

The Quadruple Helix Model of innovation recognizes four major actors in the innovation system: science, policy, industry, and society. (Shültz et al 2019)

Measures

A step planned or taken as a means to an end (Merriam Webster Dictionary). In the context of GEP implementation usually refers to an overarching measure that is implemented through various “activities”.

Monitoring

Monitoring: An ongoing function that uses the systematic collection of data related to specified indicators which provides management and the main stakeholders of a development intervention with indications of the extent of progress and achievement of expected results and progress in the use of allocated funds. Monitoring provides an early indication of the likelihood that expected results will be attained and provides an opportunity to validate the program theory and logic and to make necessary changes in program activities and approaches. (UNESCO (2007) Evaluation Handbook)

Performance Indicator

A quantitative or qualitative variable that allows the verification of a change brought about by an intervention and that shows a result relative to what was planned. (UNESCO (2007) Evaluation Handbook.)

Objective

A statement of a desired program/intervention result that meets the criteria of being Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Realistic, and Time-phased (SMART). (UNAIDS)

Outcome

A short-term or medium-term effect of an intervention’s outputs. It can be positive or negative, expected or unexpected. (UNESCO (2007) Evaluation Handbook)

Output

A tangible product, capital good, event or service that results from an intervention. Outputs such as for example the number of participants, or number of training seminars delivered, will serve as a monitoring indicator during the implementation analysis. They provide evidence if activities have been carried out as planned. (UNESCO (2007) Evaluation Handbook)

Summative Evaluation

A study conducted at the end of an intervention (or a phase of that intervention) to determine the extent to which anticipated outcomes were produced. Summative evaluation is intended to provide information about the worth of the program. (OECD 2002).

Social Network Analysis

“Social network analysis takes as its starting point the premise that social life is created primarily and most importantly by relations and the patterns formed by these relations”. (Marin and Wellman 2014) Thus, it is an actor’s position in a network that determines in part the constraints and opportunities that they will encounter; identifying these positions is important for saying something about behavior or beliefs (Borgatti, Everett, and Johnson 2013).

Target

The objective a program/intervention is working towards, expressed as a measurable value; the desired value for an indicator at a particular point in time. (UNAIDS)

Theory of Change

A ‘theory of change’ explains how activities are understood to produce a series of results that contribute to achieving the final intended impacts. It can be developed for any level of intervention – an event, a project, a program, a policy, a strategy or an organization. A theory of change can be developed for an intervention: where objectives and activities can be identified and tightly planned beforehand, or that changes and adapts in response to emerging issues and to decisions made by partners and other stakeholders. (Better Evaluation).

Triangulation

The use of three or more theories, sources or types of information, or types of analysis to verify and substantiate an assessment. Note: by combining multiple datasources, methods, analyses or theories, evaluators seek to overcome the bias that comes from single informants, single methods, single observer or single theory studies. (OECD 2002).

Validity

The extent to which the data collection strategies and instruments measure what they purport to measure. (OECD 2002)

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose, scope and structure of the deliverable

The present document includes the methodology for evaluating the GEPs designed and implemented within the CALIPER project. It is composed by two main parts: the methodology for the “formative evaluation” and the one for the “summative evaluation”.

The main scope of the deliverable is to provide to CALIPER’s partners with the methodological framework as well practical guidance on the implementation of the formative evaluation during the two iteration phases.

Chapter n. 2 introduces the concept of evaluation specifying its main components and methods. Chapter 3 focuses on the “formative evaluation”, introducing the main components and supporting templates to be used for evaluating the design of interventions and assessing the efficiency of their implementation. Chapter 4 guides the GE Working Groups in planning and carrying out the formative evaluation of their GEPs. Finally, Chapter 5 introduces the “summative evaluation” methodology which will be carried out by external, independent experts.

1.2 Relation to other WPs & Tasks

The WP4 methodology is strictly connected with WP3 on the implementation of the GEPs. Indeed, the formative evaluation is structured on the basis of the GEPs’ implementation iterations. Also the methodology will collect information which will partially feed into deliverables due within WP3 (in particular D3.1 “GEPs implementation during phase 1”), in order to make the data and information collection process as efficient as possible.

The evaluation methodology will be applied on the GEPs included in D2.3 “GEPs”, which will be eventually updated if any adjustment are required within each institution’s approval process.

The content of the present document was presented to the CALIPER’s partners during a webinar organized by Smart Venice and FUOC on the 7th of July 2021. The webinar was aimed at introducing partners to the methodological framework used in elaborating the methodology, explaining in what formative and summative evaluation consist of, providing with some examples of indicators as well as presenting chapter n. 4 about the formative methodology into practice.

2 What is evaluation?

Evaluation is the “systematic assessment of the worth or merit of an object or intervention”³. An intervention has *merit* if it performs well according to its purpose. It concerns the quality and efficiency of a given intervention. *Worth* in contrast assesses if an intervention addresses a real need. Evaluations aim to understand “**what works or does not work, how, for whom, and why**” (Kingsley 2020).

This definition goes beyond one of the earliest and still most widely used definitions which conceives evaluation simply as determining whether certain goals have been reached. Such a too simplistic assessment is insufficient as intervention goals might be corrupt, dysfunctional, unimportant or fail to address the needs of the intended beneficiaries.

It is important to note that evaluation involves **value judgements**. As Bovens, Hart, and Kuipers (2008) sustain, *evaluation is the continuation of politics with other means*. Scales of measurement, indicators of quality or definitions of success and failure are highly contested, value laden social constructions. Evaluations thus not only provide feedback on the very “effectiveness” of certain measures (its merit) but also imply an agreement on its worth, i.e. does it address a real need.

2.1 Main Components of an Evaluation

The aim of any solid evaluation is to respond to three questions regarding the (a) design of an intervention, its (b) implementation, and the (c) outcomes/ impact of the intervention:

- (a) **Design.** An evaluation should assess if an **intervention was well conceived**. An intervention is well designed if it addresses the needs of specific audience with realistic actions to achieve the desired outcomes and impact. The analysis of the design provides insights if the right “tools” have been chosen for the “right” goal. Both, summative and formative evaluations require a deep understanding of the design of an intervention.
- (b) **Implementation.** An analysis of implementation will assess if a given **intervention has been implemented efficiently**. The most well designed intervention might break down if it is only poorly executed, such as for example without sufficient resources or failing to involve decision makers. An implementation analysis is important especially for formative evaluations as it can identify problems and devise corrective measures during the execution of an intervention.
- (c) **Outcomes & Impact.** An evaluation should provide answers regarding the **effects of an intervention**. What changes – both desired and unintended, positive or negative – can be attributed to a given intervention? Identifying outcomes (short-term or medium-term) and impact (long-term) is challenging as the observed change might be the result of many factors besides the actual intervention; it might also be challenging because an effect is not immediately visible. The analysis of outcomes and impact is often the principal goal of a summative evaluation.

Each of these three evaluation objectives comes with a set of instruments and tasks to be carried out. The overall evaluation methodology proposed in this document is based upon the H2020 Efforti project⁴. In what follows, we will briefly introduce the specific tasks as part of the formative evaluation methodology.

³ See the widely shared standard definition by the Joint Committee on Standards for Educational Evaluation <https://evaluationstandards.org/> See also the *Glossary of Key Terms in Evaluation* published by the OECD (<https://www.oecd.org/dac/evaluation/2754804.pdf>)

⁴See Efforti - Evaluation Framework for Gender Equality Interventions in R&I <https://www.efforti.eu>

2.2 Methods

Evaluation requires the gathering of **primary and secondary data**. Primary data concerns the gathering of data which is unique to the intervention and does not exist beforehand. The results of survey among workshop participants is an example of primary data. Secondary data sources refer to data what has already by collected and is available in the form of reports, statistical data sources or scientific publications among other.

There is not one specific method for gathering data and the choice of an adequate method basically depends upon the evaluation question that needs answering. Social science research methods are plagued with the distinction between “quantitative” and “qualitative” data. Although this distinction has been criticized extensively (Lund 2005), it is worth mentioning the primary purpose of each.

- **Quantitative data** collected via questionnaires and surveys are suitable for assessing how widespread and general a given phenomenon is. Many psychological constructs such as “motivation”, “satisfaction” or “attitudes” can be measured in precise ways. When used in conjunction with the right statistical techniques, it enables one to generalize findings. Use quantitative data when the concepts of interest can be standardized and should be generalizable.
- **Qualitative data** aim to capture subjective understandings and meanings of actors. When used during interviews or participant observations, it aims to understand from an endemic point of view how actors perceive and act. Use qualitative methods to explore the idiosyncrasies, histories, trajectories and subjective understandings of an intervention.

It is important that both – quantitative and qualitative data – adhere to **quality standards** in the social science. Quality indicators do exist for both quantitative measures as well as qualitative and mixed-methods research (Flick 2008).

For quantitative data, it is important to note that the **quality of the evidence** gathered is fundamentally conditioned by the **quality of the measurement instruments** used. Using questionnaires or certain quantitative monitoring indicators does not automatically imply that high quality data is gathered.

Measurement instruments for the social sciences and for evaluation need to be “calibrated”, i.e. carefully tested to see if they actually measure what they are supposed to measure in a **valid** and **reliable** way.

TO KNOW MORE

Validity indicates that a given indicator actually measures the concept it is supposed to measure. For example, questions and answer options that should measure work-life balance could target only working time-arrangements or be more specific and inquire about the degree with which work interferes with private life and vice versa. **Validity implies a theoretical argument regarding how a certain social phenomena is conceived and manifest.** Problematic are indicators that are supposed to measure social phenomena which rely upon a very fuzzy definition of the construct itself. What is meant by “job satisfaction” or “living standard” is not straight forward to answer.

Reliability refers to the overall consistency of a measure. A given measure is said to be reliable if it produces similar results over time, on different occasions, or different people performing the measurement. Reliability of measurement is important especially for documenting change over time; only if an instrument is reliable you can be sure that detected changes are due to a changing social reality and not a “mal-functioning” measurement instrument. Reliability does not imply validity. A reliable measure which produces consistent results under varying conditions does not imply that it measures the phenomena of interest.

2.3 Other Useful References and Resources

BetterEvaluation website <https://www.betterevaluation.org>

Efforti project website: <https://www.efforti.eu>

Kingsley, Isabelle. 2020. "Evaluating STEM Gender Equity Programs. A Guide to Effective Program Evaluation." University of New South Wales.

Bryman, Alan. 2008. *Social Research Methods*. 3. ed. Oxford: Oxford Univ. Press.

Hesse-Biber, Sharlene, ed. 2012. *Handbook of Feminist Research: Theory and Praxis*. Thousand Oaks, US: SAGE Publications, Inc. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781483384740>.

3 Formative Evaluation Methodology

This section will guide Caliper GE Working Groups in implementing RPO/RFO to plan and carry out the formative evaluation of their GEP. As such it will introduce the main components and supporting templates to be used for evaluating the **design of interventions** and assessing the **efficiency of their implementation**⁵.

To recall: the formative evaluation takes place during the project's lifespan and is aimed at getting feedback while an action is being implemented to ensure its progress complies with planning. The formative evaluation will therefore feed into certain key action points through various iterative phases of the GEP to facilitate their smooth implementation.

Naturally, the evaluation of the design of the intervention is closely **aligned with the actual GEP design**. The formative evaluation at this stage can be seen as a set of instruments to help create well-designed interventions.

Evaluation needs to be considered from the beginning of GEP design to enable effective feedback loops, strengthen the implementation process as well as provide the basis for an accurate summative evaluation to be carried out. GEPs should include explicit objectives as well as actions, identify those responsible for the action, targets and timeframe. Objectives should be evidenced based and closely linked to the main audit results.

TO KNOW MORE

See guidelines developed by the H2020 TARGET project, TARGET Guidelines: How to design customised GEPs

Please see the timeline for the evaluation process on the following page. Both the formative and summative evaluation processes are included in this timeline to enable a holistic understanding of the evaluation process.

⁵The analysis of outcomes and impacts will be the focus of the summative evaluation, to be carried out by an independent evaluator.

Figure 1: Timing of evaluation activities in the Caliper project

3.1 Design Evaluation

Evaluating the design of an intervention is done largely via desktop research, seeking answers to the following questions:

- **Who** is the **audience** of the intervention, who is addressed? For example, PhD candidates or school teachers?
- **What are the goals** of an intervention? For example, to attract more girls to STEM careers.
- **What** are the expected **outcomes and impact**? For example, to provide less stereotypical career choices.
- **Which activities** are planned? For example, an awareness raising campaign.
- **What** are **suitable indicators** to monitor progress? For example, more female students in STEM degree courses.
- **Which resources** are available to implement the intervention? Part-time position; collaboration with NGO.

As known, the design of the GEPs is relying on results from the internal and external assessments carried out according to “D1.1. Internal and External Assessment Methodologies and Guidelines” of the Caliper project. Further useful references regarding research methods are available in Casillas et al. (2020) and Bryman (2008).

In order to articulate the overall workings of an intervention, the above-mentioned elements are brought together by a so-called “log-frame”. A log-frame is an instrument to **build an overarching story** about how a specific GEP intervention is supposed to work.

In addition to the analysis of the target audience, the goals and activities, a log-frame incorporates an analysis of the facilitating and hindering **contextual factors** of an intervention. National or regional policy frameworks are such contextual factors together with the organizational working environment.

A log-frame furthermore provides an instrument to create an awareness of the **complexity involved** for initiating and sustaining organizational change processes. Good log-frames consult the existing scientific literature to provide evidence on the likelihood of certain interventions to be successful.

TO KNOW MORE

Log-frames are an instrument to put a “theory of change” in practice. “Theory of Change set out the framework for telling a credible performance story of an intervention. As such, a verified or partially verified “theory of change” can be used as the basis for reporting on what contribution the intervention has made” (Mayne and Johnson 2015; Vogel 2012).

A “theory of change” highlights the importance of context for understanding change, while recognizing its complexity in order to explain impact. There is a “substantial body of evidence that the complex combination of structural, cultural, institutional and economic factors that create barriers for women in science, engineering and technology (SET) require a correspondingly integrated and sophisticated strategic and operational response.” (Kalpazidou Schmidt and Cacace 2017).

As in CALIPER the decision was made to align the GEPs’ design as much as possible with the design of the evaluation methodology, the log-frame template provided on page 17 will be the main instrument for carrying out both the design of the actions to be included in the GEPs, and the design evaluation after the planned interventions of GEPs have been carried out. This has been developed specifically for the CALIPER project. It is an adapted version of EFFORTI log-frame template which is available under the following address <https://efforti.eu/efforti-toolbox-intro>

The log-frame template introduces the main building blocks for the analysis of the design of an intervention. It does not specify the methodology or instruments used for gathering the available evidence – although it highlights those building blocks which require methodological choices (gray background).

Sections 2.1.1-2.1.5 of this Evaluation Methodology provides extensive advice of what to consider when filling each section of the log-frame. This is also complemented by the very detailed questions in **Error! Reference source not found.** on page **Error! Bookmark not defined.** as well as the **Error! Reference source not found.** on page **Error! Bookmark not defined.**

Figure 2: Evaluation Design Template (log-frame)

In what follows, we will introduce each element of the log-frame in more detail, using a concrete intervention example. The example is a specifically adapted version of a **mentoring program for early career researchers** taken from the Efforti Impact Story Knowledge Base⁶.

CONCRETE EXAMPLE

As women are underrepresented in research and leadership positions within academia, the purpose of mentoring programs are to contribute to improving the female talent pool for career progression by strengthening women mentees' professional and/or leadership skills and career prospects through planning, prioritising, networking and insights into organisational norms, processes and policies.

Mentoring schemes may take different forms and have different objectives. However, most definitions agree that a mentoring relationship typically involves an experienced (older) mentor who guides, advises, and supports a less experienced mentee (Chandler 1996).

A summary fiche of the intervention on which our examples is based is available <https://efforti.eu/node/61>

3.1.1 Audience: For Whom?

A first step of the formative evaluation is to determine the **program participants**. Who will participate in the intervention? Who should benefit from a program?

Determining the target audience implies not only identifying potential beneficiaries but also to **think about their characteristics** and start defining their **needs**.

The audience might be more diverse than initially imagined, including the involvement of external partners such as NGOs or friends and family of the main beneficiary.

At this early stage it is also recommended to think about who will be interested in the evaluation results? The **evaluation audience - who is the evaluation for** – will help you to understand better the evaluation priorities. It facilitates to spell out the implications of the evaluation results according to the different needs of Human Resource staff, external sponsors, or policy makers, for example.

CONCRETE EXAMPLE

The starting point of the mentoring program is the high attrition rate of young female researchers. Hence, the **program participants** are firstly young female researchers at the post-doc level and assistant professor levels.

Secondly, the GEP working group also recognize that the university has **experienced staff** as associate or full professors who can share their experiences of successfully navigating their career path within the university.

Thirdly, GEP working group identifies the **evaluation audience**. The evaluation will be of interest to human resources, as well as the different departments, faculties and institutes that suffer the attrition of young post-doc talented women researchers. Other universities facing similar problems as well as various companies in the local eco-system and in particular technological firms might be interested in the findings as well.

⁶See https://efforti.eu/sites/default/files/interventions/Impact%20Story_AU_Mentoring%20Programme.pdf

3.1.2 Goals: To achieve what?

The goals specify what a given intervention aims to achieve for its program participants and beyond. Goals can be very concrete or rather abstract. However, by making goals “SMART” and dividing them into “outcomes” and “impact”, goals can be made very concise and tangible.

By **outcome** we mean the immediate effects of the program on participants. These usually refers to changes in attitudes, knowledge & skills, motivation, interests, or behavior of participants which can be observed immediately or over a relative short period of time. Outcomes can be subdivided in **short-term** (less than 1 year) or **medium-term** outcomes (1 to 2 years).

For example, a short-term outcome of a training workshop on “speaking in public” could be a boost in self-confidence among participants. A medium-term outcome of such a seminar could be an increased participation in conferences or public discussions.

By **impact** we mean consequences of a program beyond its direct and immediate interaction with the recipients. The impact of an intervention is broader in scope in terms of affected changes and audiences. A program can have impact across different dimensions, including among others, economic- (e.g. competitiveness), social- (e.g. equality, social cohesion), or technology and innovation (e.g. new services, products, standardization, etc.) impacts. In order for an intervention to achieve impact beyond program participants, its effects need to be observed **over a longer period of time** (3 to 5 years) considering its intended and unintended effects.

For example, the impact of a training workshop on “speaking in public” could be an increased awareness among conference organizers of women experts for discussion panels and more gender balanced expert, peer review committees.

When defining the goals of an intervention it is helpful to make them **SMART**. This refers to : Specific / Measurable/ Achievable/ Relevant/ Time Specific. Yemm (2012) explains how to develop SMART objectives:

Specific (which is where many go wrong from the start and make things too vague). This step should make things explicit so that there is no room for misinterpretation

The following questions can help to keep this step specific:

- what needs to be done (Express this as a positive, e.g, “We will build...”, “I will save ..” Aim to use action verbs when you can.
- what will be the outcome or result?
- Why is this important?
- Who is responsible? Who else needs to be involved?
- What requirements/ constraints are involved?

Measurable

Many objectives are easy to measure because they are quantifiable and use numbers or percentages or produce a finite outcome. We can track these results easily. The challenge is for the more qualitative objectives where the outcome might be more subjective. With these you need to be able to define the behavioral criteria or evidence which will indicate that the outcomes is what is wanted. Although not true every time, if you cannot answer the question, “How will you, or others know you have achieved XXX?” it is probably not specific enough.

Achievable

Setting the objectives at the right level is a key element. They need to be stretching and ambitious but not so much that they are unachievable- At the same time, making objectives too easy will not be motivating.

These questions can help with this step:

- Is this objective within my control?
- Can I/ we get it done in the proposed time frame?
- Do I understand the limitations and constraints?
- Can we do this with the resources we have?
- Is this possible and practical?

Relevant

Individuals and the team need to see how the objective is relevant to their role and the overall direction of the team. This enables people to see how their work is contributing to the overall organization objectives. Another aspect of being relevant is to ensure that the different objectives are supporting each other and not creating any conflicts or tensions.

Time specific

Most of us work better to deadlines. This step is about setting the deadline for the achievement of the objective. It creates a sense of urgency required to execute tasks for many people. Deadlines create the focus and help to set priority and prompt action.

There is one simple question:

- When will this objective be completed?

CONCRETE EXAMPLE

The mentoring intervention defined several overarching goals:

- to increase the talent pool at the university, specifically by increasing the number of women in R&I positions
- to improve working environment, specifically the working conditions and work-life balance
- to boost professional capabilities in terms of career planning, networking and professional competences

The GEP working group then specified short-term, medium-term outcomes as well as the potential impact of the intervention.

Short-term outcomes: foster confidence, well-being and job satisfaction of individual mentees as well as improved knowledge and understanding of advancement prerequisites and career strategies and clarification of career prospects and wishes. For mentors, the intervention is likely to increase their intrinsic motivation and satisfaction to “do something good” for a young researcher.

Medium-range outcomes: improved networking and career prospects for mentees through access to mentors professional network. Increased efficiency in time management and prioritizing tasks. Attraction and retention of young researchers. Greater awareness of gender issues in scientific careers.

The following effects of the mentoring program beyond the direct participants and over a longer period of time are also specified.

Long-term impact: Increase the female talent pool at the organization. The intervention will raise awareness on gender structures at the University and contribute to change organisational structures and culture, including better integration of women in the research environment. Overall, the intervention is expected to improve the quality of the working climate by increasing collegial support, knowledge-sharing, network facilitation and collaboration across seniority ranks.

3.1.3 Activities: What to do?

Describe **the activities that will be carried out** in order to achieve the program goals? Participants will have to engage in one or several exercises over an extended period of time. As these activities need to be organized, the evaluation of the design should include an assessment of the required “inputs” and the likely “outputs”.

Input refers to the resources needed to implement an activity. Inputs are usually subdivided into:

- (a) time - how long will it take to carry out the activity? For example, 2 three hour workshops + 2 working days for preparation of the workshop, 1 working day for analyzing evaluation results.
- (b) human - how many persons are needed to carry out an activity? For example, 1 expert trainer and 2 volunteer facilitators
- (c) financial – budget. For example, travel costs for participants or speaker fees.
- (d) material - rooms, consumables, pens, charts, etc.

Planned activities need to be realistic in terms of the required investment.

CONCRETE EXAMPLE

To achieve the planned goals of the mentoring program the GEP working group in conjunction with the Human Resources Department developed a **year long mentoring program targeting 40 young female post-docs and assistant professors**.

The **main activity** consists of **meetings between mentors and mentees**. Meetings last between one and two hours, with five meetings being distributed over the year. Topics discussed include e.g. career opportunities, publication strategies, prioritizing (research, teaching, general workload and work-life balance), as well as project applications, navigation in the research environment.

The mentoring is a **low budget intervention**. Mentors work on a voluntary basis. HR staff is responsible for organizing the meetings as well as initially matching mentors and mentees, organize a workshop to introduce the program and do a limited evaluation of every round of the program.

Outputs of an activity refers to simple numeric indicators that capture the characteristics of the activity. To continue with the above example, this could simply refer to the number of mentors-mentee meetings carried out (see also section 2.2.7 Monitoring Indicators on page 32ff).

3.1.4 Facilitating & Hindering Contextual Factors

In order to assess the design of an intervention, several contextual factors should be considered. Interventions do not happen in a vacuum but need to be seen within the wider organizational and national environment which is likely to affect its implementation, outcomes and impact.

An analysis of the wider context also provides important insights on the framing of an intervention – there might

be parallel initiatives or previous (good/bad) experiences which need to be considered.

Policy context. The policy context of an intervention captures the wider facilitating or hindering legislative framework of an intervention. This usually includes wider policy frameworks for (gender) equality or diversity but also policy for R&D and Innovation system. Policy frameworks exist on different geographical scales and can range from EU wide, to national and regional policies. For example, the design and implementation of a GEP is likely to be facilitated with references to equality and/or non-discrimination legislation at the national level.

Organizational context. The working environment with its organizational cultures and climate is likely to affect an intervention. These include strategic plans, the organizational goals and ambitions which might be more (or less) receptive to equality interventions.

History / past interventions. Interventions might come in waves or several editions. Past experience and positive (or negative) reception of certain activities within an organization contain important clues as to the likely outcomes and impact of a planned activity. There might be a “fatigue” among participants due to previous similar interventions; there might be synergies to explore with similar interventions.

Collaborations. Existing collaborations and networks with the wider R&I Ecosystem of the organization can provide important hinder or supporting factors. Diverse external stakeholders can provide support in terms of experience, advice, best practice. They can also offer competing solutions – which might diminish the success of an internally organized action.

CONCRETE EXAMPLE

Several contextual factors influence the implementation and the likely outcomes and impact of the mentoring program that was developed and implemented in Denmark.

Policy context. The Act on Equal Treatment, the Act on Equal Pay for Men and Women, and the Act on Entitlement to Leave and Benefits in the Event of Childbirth states that any kind of discrimination on the Danish labor market is prohibited. However, in general, structural gender biases are often overlooked or neglected in Denmark, because the common perception is that men and women are equal and have equal opportunities in Denmark. Simultaneously government, public and private organizations all encourage everybody to prevent discrimination and strive to achieve GE.

Organizational context. A significant influencer is top management support to initiate and implement this type of mentoring intervention is crucial (Kalpazidou Schmidt and Cacace 2017; Cacace et al. 2015). Besides the support of the leadership, the case of the mentoring program also points to the importance of bottom up support, e.g. the willingness of tenured faculty to function as mentors as well as the willingness of early career scholars to participate in the program. The university management may support the intervention, i.e. top-down initiated and through financial backing.

History / previous interventions: In 2010 a pilot mentoring scheme was initiated as a collaboration between human resources (HR) at members of EU project WHIST. In 2013, a permanent mentoring program was launched by the University Human Resources Department labeled “Empower Talent!”. The mentoring program was embedded in another EU project STAGES.

Collaborations: A mentoring network has been established in a comparable university within the same city. The support and experiences of this initiative provides important insights on the success factors for the implementation process.

3.1.5 Theoretical assumptions and available evidence

An important but often neglected resource for assessing the design of an intervention are of course past

evaluations! Emerging from EU funded gender equality projects but also other sources, has produced a growing knowledge base regarding the effectiveness of all different types of interventions.

TO KNOW MORE

The Efforti Impact Story Knowledge Base, for example, provides a collection of 17 different types of interventions + their evaluations. The fact sheets provide detailed descriptions regarding the audience, goals, activities, outcomes and impacts as well as monitoring indicators for organizational interventions to large scale national programs.

The Impact Story Knowledge is online at https://efforti.eu/impact_story

Beyond the Efforti toolbox, Google Scholar provides access to many scientific publications regarding the topic of interest. For example, a quick search⁷ with the keywords “academic mentoring women program” since 2019 provides among the first hits a systematic review of mentoring models in academic medicine.

Farkas, Amy H., Eliana Bonifacino, Rose Turner, Sarah A. Tilstra, and Jennifer A. Corbelli. 2019. “Mentorship of Women in Academic Medicine: A Systematic Review.” *Journal of General Internal Medicine* 34 (7): 1322–29. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11606-019-04955-2>.

This article provides a first orientation regarding the **key success factors** – including their empirical evidence - of mentoring programs.

CONCRETE EXAMPLE

Going over the Efforti Impact Story of the mentoring program identifies several difficulties that could be addressed in similar and future interventions.

Critics point to how mentoring schemes target individual women as opposed to organisational structures and culture, in efforts to “fix the women” as opposed to “fixing the organisation”. As such mentoring cannot stand alone in improving gender equality in organisations (Kalpazidou Schmidt and Cacace, 2018; van den Brink and Benschop, 2012).

Finally to be effective mentoring schemes need to be intersectional in order to successfully include and positively support all women in need of mentoring and allowing equal access to the programme (Chandler, 1996).

3.1.6 Methods & instruments

The set of research methods to be used during the assessment of the design of an intervention is relatively small. Most required information can be gathered through desktop research. To the degree that the analysis is part of a formative evaluation carried out by a Gender Equality working group whose members have been involved in the conceptualization of the intervention, this information will be readily available.

The overarching methodological instrument is the “log-frame”. Filling in the log-frame template as shown on page 19 enables an evaluator to “tell the story” how a given intervention is supposed to work. In order to work on the different question blocks, some methodological choices are available, listed in the following table.

⁷https://scholar.google.es/scholar?as_ylo=2019&q=academic+mentoring+women+program&hl=es&as_sdt=0,5

Evaluation Building Block	Methods	Sources
Context Factors (Policy, organizational, historical, key actors)	Document analysis (see e.g. Bowen 2009)	Organizational websites, reports, strategic plans
	Comparative research (see e.g. Mills, van de Bunt, and de Bruijn 2006)	
	Descriptive statistics analysis	Official statistics, secondary data sources
Tested assumptions and empirical evidence	Literature research, e.g. systematic or scoping reviews (see e.g. Munn et al. 2018)	Scientific literature, academic search engines, subject relevant archives, committees, organizations (GenPORT, EIGE, National Academy of Sciences, etc.)
Overall design of intervention (goals, audiences, activities, targets)	Semi-structured interviews (Casillas et al. 2020; Bryman 2008)	Member of intervention planning group, key institutional stakeholders including decision makers
	Focus group (Casillas et al. 2020; Bryman 2008)	Member(s) of the intervention planning group

Table 1: Evaluation research methods

Although the design evaluation focuses on the targets and short-term, medium-term and long-term indicators of the intervention, it does not specify the methods for collecting the corresponding data. This will happen during the implementation assessment (see next section) and the summative evaluation (impact assessment).

3.1.7 Summary

As a result of working through the log-frame template, already since the design phase of the GEPs' actions a detailed picture should emerge of how a given intervention is supposed to work. It should identify the core underlying problems that need to be addressed, the envisioned change and activities and resources that will be required. Taking into account various contextual factors as well as the available evidence from similar interventions, a solid conceptual understanding of the planned intervention has been achieved.

Evaluating the design of the intervention at the end of each implementation cycle, will imply reviewing the initially filled in log-frames based on information and data gathered through the implementation analysis (see dedicated section below):

- for those actions that will be continued and prolonged in the second GEP's iteration, the log-frame will be reviewed comparing and contrasting the first versions with the new one, highlighting all changes/updates in the text, as well as providing short explanations on the reasons behind changes and adaptations, as well as critical meta-reflections on possible mistakes/biases having occurred in the design phase and their roots (assessment phase in WP1 or co-creation phase in WP2).

- for those actions that will be discontinued in the second iteration and for the last formative evaluation cycle at the end of the second iteration, design evaluation will consist of short paragraphs commenting on each action's log-frames and explaining if results from implementation analysis confirmed the adequacy of the design in its building blocks or if any of those was for any reasons flawed or partial, and how, therefore which lessons have been learned from that.

3.2 Implementation Analysis

The main aim of the formative evaluation is to oversee and steer the implementation of GEP interventions. Monitoring indicators have to be developed and applied in order to detect if a program is on-track – or highlight if there is a problem with implementation that needs to be addressed. The implementation analysis will contrast the actual implementation of a given intervention compared to how it was initially envisioned.

Changing the way people and organizations work is difficult and takes time. **Resistance to change is part and parcel of any GEP process** and should be expected. The implementation analysis provides a way to detect, document and deal with resistance to change.

Monitoring data can provide useful information regarding the quality of the implementation process. If a program fails to produce the desired results, it is important to understand if a weak outcome is the result of “bad” design or “bad” implementation (Rogers et al. 2015).

Regarding the **overall timing and execution**, the implementation analysis will be carried out from month 18 to month 46 (see page 14 for the timeline of this process). The evaluation methodology described in this section serves as a basis for the organizations to establish their own self-assessment procedure, including the development of monitoring indicators.

The implementation analysis is a continuous process divided into 2 iteration phases. The **first iteration phase** runs from M18-M30 with a first formative evaluation report due in M31. The **second iteration phase** runs from M32 to M44 with the second self-assessment report due in M46. The self-assessment that accompanies the implementation process will enable the institution to critically reflect on- and steer the embedding of the GEP within its organization. The self-assessment reports will also provide input to the external (summative) evaluation towards the end of the project.

Overall, the implementation analysis comprises several **building blocks**, seeking answers regarding the following points.

- Which **key actions** are implemented? This is based upon the initial design of the GEP measures. The implementation analysis starts from the initial planning of measures and needs to document to which degree these have been carried out.
- Who are the **key actors involved**? Identifying key actors is a first step in order to understand how responsibilities and decision making is distributed.
- What **organizational processes** have been established and need to be considered? This is important as decision making and responsibilities are distributed across departments, councils, and other organizational units, also considering that change in organizational processes in part of the ultimate GEPs goals.
- The overall evaluation priority/question concerns to assess any **changes of the intervention** with respect to the planned goals, activities, audiences, targets.

The following diagram summarizes the main building blocks for carrying out an implementation analysis.

Figure 3: Template for monitoring of implementation process

3.2.1 Key Actions

On a very general level, the implementation analysis will need to keep track of the type and number of actions implemented. During the design phase of the GEP, a list of activities are outlined to achieve the specified objectives. This can range from training seminars, to revision of recruitment procedures, to the constitution of working groups, etc.

The implementation of specific actions usually comprises a set of specific sub-tasks to be carried out. The implementation analysis keeps track of the planned actions and sub-tasks and simply annotates if these activities have been carried out or not. Not all foreseen activities might be possible to implement during the available time frame and resources.

Differences in terms of planned and implemented activities need to be addressed and where possible corrected.

3.2.2 Key Actors

Any implementation of GE interventions is likely to involve several people – beyond the target beneficiaries. As more people get involved, the management of implementation gets more challenging as tasks and responsibilities need to be distributed and coordinated.

The implementation analysis identifies key actors with their corresponding responsibilities. An effective implementation distributes responsibilities across actors, guarantees redundancies to avoid bottle necks regarding key competencies and makes sure that decision makers are involved.

The implementation analysis answers the following questions:

- Who is involved during the implementation. How will drop-out/absence of one affect the implementation?
- What is the responsibility and competence of each involved actor?
- Are required decision makers involved?
- Are there any individuals that stand out as particularly enabling or hindering the implementation?
- Do all involved actors share a common understanding of the intervention? Is everybody on the “same page”? Misunderstandings of concepts and aims can easily lead to implementation failure.

CONCRETE EXAMPLE

The mentoring program at the university was setup with the involvement of the Gender Equality working group and one person from Human Resources. Recruitment of mentors and mentees was organized by HR staff through a university wide campaign. Importantly, the communication department was involved in raising the overall visibility of the mentoring scheme among academic staff in order to recruit a sufficiently large and diverse set of mentors.

Crucially, the scientific management of the university was involved in order to provide incentives to academic staff in terms of recognizing and rewarding mentoring activities in their internal performance evaluation.

3.2.3 Key Processes

The implementation analysis needs to examine the administrative and organizational processes required for

carrying out an intervention. The analysis will provide evidence regarding the challenges and obstacles to achieve organizational change. It builds upon the key actors identified in the previous step, now examining in detail the decision making processes, organizational hierarchies and responsibilities involved. It responds to the following questions, regarding:

- **Organizational processes.** How is the overall implementation process organized? Is there a fixed working group whose members meet on a regular basis? How are decision making processes organized? Is there a clear understanding of the wider organizational procedures that need to get involved? Are organizational decision-making bodies involved?
- **Timing of tasks.** Was/is the timing of the activities realistic? To the degree that tasks are interdependent and involve broader organizational processes, does the execution of tasks provided for enough leeway in order to compensate for delays? Does the timing of the tasks allow for the internal duration of administrative processes?
- **Synergies and sustainability.** Implementation can be boosted by tapping into parallel or complementary activities within the organization. Are there similar interventions (past and present) which condition the implementation? If so, how?

CONCRETE EXAMPLE

The mentoring program at the university established a working group for setting up and running the program which involved the Gender Equality working group, one person from HR initially. The working group agreed upon bi-weekly meetings at a fixed time; a virtual working space for sharing documents was setup.

The meeting and involvement of the universities scientific steering group was planned well ahead in order to provide for a revision of the new performance assessment criteria – incorporating mentoring activities.

The implementation was boosted along these lines by coordinating with an internal working commission for the revision of excellence criteria in scientific careers.

3.2.4 Evaluation Priorities & Questions

Evaluation priorities and evaluation questions (in the following section) can be divided into generic priorities, concerned with the overall implementation process and those priorities/questions that address the content of each specific intervention in particular.

Generic Priorities and Questions – Any Intervention

The overall evaluation priority regarding the implementation of an intervention concerns the assessment of deviations, obstacles, or challenges that emerge during the process. The evaluation priority concentrates on assessing the effective implementation of the measure. Simple, straight forward questions to be asked are:

- To what extent does the implementation deviate from the plan? Has it changed and has been adapted? This can concern any item of the design: audience, goals, activities, desired outcomes and foreseen impact.
- What barriers and obstacles have been encountered during the implementation? Have these barriers been overcome?
- What factors inhibit or facilitate the implementation of the intervention? Are these factors in line with the goals of the intervention?

Specific Priorities and Questions – Adapted to Particular Intervention

Specific priorities and questions depend upon each action to be implemented and should be developed in collaboration with Smart-Venice/VIL and the capacity building activities.

3.2.5 Methods - Overview

The implementation analysis makes use of wide ranging methods and instruments in order to gather the necessary data on actors, organizational processes, the ongoing activities and first outcomes. The following table provides an overview of the main building blocks of the implementation analysis and their respective instruments for data collection.

Evaluation Building Block		Methods	Sources
Evaluation Priorities / Questions	Questions regarding key actors, key processes. Changes over time, facilitating and hindering factors.	Focus Group, Semi-structure interviews	Stakeholders involved in implementation; not members of GE working group
Targets & Indicators	Output (direct services, products or events produced by activities)	Documentation	Intervention organizers.
	Outcome – Short-term (Post-test, pretest-post-test, etc.)	Polls, questionnaires, organizational statistics and indicators	Beneficiaries, participants
	Outcome – medium-term (Time-series)	Polls, questionnaires, interviews, organizational statistics and indicators	Beneficiaries, participants

Table 2: main building blocks of the implementation analysis

3.2.6 Monitoring the overall implementation process

Qualitative data on the overall implementation process will be gathered with at least one focus group and **7 x semi-structured interviews**. In contrast to those actors involved in the design of the intervention, the implementation analysis should focus on other involved stakeholders.

At least **1 x focus group** involving the key actors for implementing the intervention should be organized. This is an opportunity to query participants experiences, identify obstacles and gauge to which degree the actual implementation matches the goals, activities and outcomes.

Methodological guidance to carry out interviews and focus groups is available in “D1.1. Internal and External Assessment Methodologies and Guidelines” as well as Casillas et al. (2020), Bryman (2008) or other sources such as the Oxfam Research Guidelines on Focus Groups.

3.2.7 Monitoring Indicators

Within each institution it is necessary to set up a monitoring process in order to track the implementation progress as well as document any changes in the status quo of gender equality. The monitoring indicators need to be **developed and “owned” by each implementing organization** as these **indicators are specific** to the GEP

objectives, implemented measures and corresponding tasks/activities of each organization.

The implementation analysis distinguished between several type of monitoring indicators (see also the section on “Goals: To achieve what?” page 21 of the design evaluation):

Output indicators. Provide a simple, numerical tracking regarding the main features of an implemented action. This usually refers to the number and type of training activities, the number of participants, the number of materials produced or procedures revised. It’s the direct, material result of an activity. The documentation of activities does not require specific data collection methods.

Short-term outcome indicators. Capture the immediate to short-term effects of an activity. This can already require specific data collection methods to document for example a change in skills, knowledge, awareness or application that result from a specific activity.

For example, workshop participants are required to fill out a questionnaire before and after the training seminar to detect if newly introduce concepts have been assimilated. Kingsley 2020 page 25ff specifies different “testing” options along these lines:

- *Posttest:* Data are collected after the program. Participants take part in the program and are tested afterwards.
- *Pretest/ posttest:* Participants receive a pretest, take part in the program and receive a posttest afterwards. The results of the pretest and posttest are compared. The difference assesses how much change the program achieved.
- *Retrospective pretest/ posttest:* Another variation of the pretest/ posttest design. Participants take both a pretest and a posttest after the program. Participants report their prior ideas retrospectively (pretest) and their current ideas (posttest). For example, participants may be asked how they felt about their skills before the program and how they feel about their skills now.

Medium-term outcome indicators. The basic difference to short-term indicators is the duration after which a specific impact is monitored. Tracking the changes of certain activities over longer periods of time becomes methodologically increasingly complex as other activities or factors can influence the overall picture.

- *Time series:* This is a variation of the pretest/posttest design. It collects data over regular intervals of time. Participants are tested before, during and after the program. The test results are compared to assess change over time intervals.

Many **relevant impact indicators** for the Caliper project are listed under section 2.2. Quantitative Indicators of “D1.1. Internal and External Assessment Methodology and Guidelines” (page 14ff).

It is important to notice, that the process of developing monitoring indicators forms part of a more comprehensive competence building exercise for the implementing institutions taking part in the CALIPER project. It is also good practice to make monitoring indicators made publicly available.

In order to provide initial guidance on how to develop and setup monitoring indicators, we present an example for each of the three ERA objectives for the gender equality: (1) removing institutionalized gendered barriers to careers; (2) promoting gender equality in decision-making and (3) integrating the gender dimension into research content and teaching.

Example Activities & Indicators – Careers

Removing gender related institutional barriers to career advancement and promotion is a well overall goal of each Gender Equality Plan. Increasing the gender balance along the entire career ladder usually involves the implementation of a series of different measures (see examples in **Error! Reference source not found.** no page

Error! Bookmark not defined.). Using again the “Mentoring scheme” as an example, the following outputs, short-term and medium-term outcome indicators can be envisioned:

Measure	Activity	Output	Outcome Indicator	
			Short-term	medium-term
Establish Mentoring Program	Establish mentoring guidelines and documents	Published training materials and didactic units for mentors and mentees	Increased awareness about the benefits, opportunities and challenges regarding mentoring program.	
	Recruitment / matching of mentors and mentees	Number of mentors recruited; number of mentees seeking support.	Matched mentor – mentee pairs.	
	Hold training seminars for mentors; mentees	Number of training seminars held; number of participants (gender)	Awareness of responsibilities and duties; challenges of mentoring relations. Adjusted expectations	Experienced mentors; mentor-to-mentor support network; expansion of professional networks.
	Mentor and mentee meetings	Number of mentor – mentee meetings held	Increased confidence, well-being, job satisfaction; improved understanding of career advancement requisites, etc.	Improved networking and career prospects for mentees, etc.
	Evaluate results; challenges and improvements for 2 nd round.	Number of focus groups and interviews carried out with mentors and mentees.	Understanding of challenges and obstacles in mentor program.	Improved mentoring program

Table 3: Example mentoring scheme measure, with potential activities, outputs, short- and medium-term outcome indicator.

The overarching goal and objective for implementing a mentoring program in terms of the envisioned long-term impact (not listed in the above table) includes: an increased talent pool at the university, an improved working environment and to boost the professional capabilities in terms of career planning, networking and professional competences.

Overall, the development of adequate outcome (short-term and medium-term) indicators needs to be adapted to the specific measures and activities described in the Gender Equality Plan of each implementing organization. The corresponding capacity building and oversight will be carried out Smart-Venice in collaboration with the implementing organization.

Example Activity & Indicators – Decision Making

In order to increase the gender balance in decision making positions, widely applied measures are listed in **Error! Reference source not found.** on page **Error! Bookmark not defined.**. Using the example of the revision of

appointment procedures for committee chairs, the following table illustrates potential short-term and medium-term outcome indicators in relation to the planned activities.

Measure	Activity	Output	Outcome Indicator	
			Short-term	medium-term
Develop election rules to foster a balanced gender composition	Map and revise existing appointment rules	Number of interviews with existing committee chairs; Collection of documents specifying appointment procedures	Awareness advantages and disadvantages of current appointment committees	
	Introduce new requirement of 50/50 gender representation for candidate pool of decision making positions	Number of revised and approved appointment rules	Share of appointment processes with 50/50 gender balanced pool of candidates	Chairs of committees are gender balanced
	Introduce term of office limits for all chairs of decision making committees	Number of revised and approved appointment rules	Number of elections for committee chairs carried out under new regulations	Number of committees with fixed term of chairs
	Introduce accountability mechanisms to appointment procedures – when gender balance cannot be met.	Number of revised and approved appointment rules	Number of notifications of gender in-balanced pool and identification of their reasons to top management	Recommendations to avoid gender imbalance in appointment procedures

Table 4: Example measure of revision of appointment procedure with with potential activities & short-, medium-term outcome indicators

Example Activity & Indicators – Gender Dimension

Integrating the gender dimension into research content and teaching is a comparatively recent activity. Nevertheless, a set of commonly applied measures has become available over the recent years different measures (see examples in **Error! Reference source not found.** on page **Error! Bookmark not defined.**). Using the example of gender proofing of the curriculum, the following table demonstrates potential activities with their corresponding outcome indicators (short-term and medium-term).

Measure	Activity	Output	Outcome Indicator	
			Short-term	medium-term
Gender proofing	Map socially relevant applications of	Number of expert interviews carried out.	Number of new didactic units addressing under-	Incorporation of more diverse topics and examples catering for

curriculum	knowledge (e.g. using student survey; desktop research).	Number of respondents to student interests poll. Number of additional topics of social relevance identified.	represented topics; incorporation of under-represented applications in existing units.	more diverse student interests in subject area.
	Revise gender-balance of key scholars / texts in field of knowledge.	Number of additional scholars/texts identified – of the under-represented gender.	More gender balanced reading list for core curriculum	Increased awareness of under-represented but important authors/scholars within field of knowledge.
	Revise topics for relevance of gender dimension	Number of revised subject areas and research methods.	Number of revised didactic units that incorporate the gender dimension	Increased awareness of the importance of the gender dimension in field of knowledge.

Table 5: Example measure, activities and corresponding short-term and medium-term outcome indicators for integrating a gender dimension into teaching

Overall, such a measure has the overarching goals to increase the interest and motivation from a more diverse student population in the curriculum. It also aims to raise the awareness of important scholars of the under-represented gender within the field (usually women) while improving the overall quality and societal relevance of scientific knowledge, engineering and technology produced.

4 Formative evaluation methodology into practice

4.1 Introduction

The present section is aimed at providing practical guidance to partners in the implementation of the formative evaluation described in chapter 3 of the present document.

As explained in the previous chapters, the main aim of formative evaluation, and in particular, of the implementation analysis, is to oversee and steer the implementation of GEP interventions.

Each partner needs to establish its own self-assessment procedure, including the development of indicators which will be periodically monitored to detect if a program is on-track or if there are any problems that need to be addressed.

4.2 Formative evaluation cycles

The formative evaluation will concern both implementation iterations and therefore take place from the beginning of the GEP implementation (M19, July 2021) till M46 (October 2023). The first iteration phase will run from M19 till M30, while the second one from M32 to M44. Within each iteration phase, 3 formative evaluation cycles will be conducted. In each evaluation cycle partners will need to collect all the relevant data according to their own “Monitoring & Evaluation Plan” (see paragraph 4.3), which will need to tackle the building blocks summarized in the figure 3 at page 29 of the present methodology.

The figures below show how the evaluation cycles should be scheduled within each iteration phase.

Figure 4: First iteration evaluation cycles

Figure 5: Second iteration evaluation cycles

4.3 Monitoring and evaluation plan

The aim of the formative evaluation is to gather all the necessary data on actors, organizational processes, the ongoing activities and the first outcomes. As already mentioned above, each partner will need to elaborate a “Monitoring & Evaluation Plan” tailored to its own GEP. The Monitoring & Evaluation Plan will have the purpose of planning the monitoring and evaluation process according to the evaluation cycles presented in the previous paragraph. It will define tools/methods and indicators in order to track the implementation progress as well as document any changes in the status quo of gender equality. The Plan will address data collection considering:

- Quantitative data: mainly through keeping a set of organizational statistics and indicators regulatory monitored;
- Qualitative data: mainly through desk research, semi-structured interviews, focus groups and questionnaires.

The monitoring and evaluation plan will need to include:

- A section related to periodic monitoring (definition of expected outputs and indicators);
- A section related to final evaluation activities for each cycle (e.g. interviews, focus groups, questionnaires, etc.):
- A timeline.

A template that partners can use for elaborating their own monitoring plan is available at the present [link](#). The Monitoring and evaluation plan should be elaborated by **the end of August 2021**.

4.3.1 Periodic monitoring activities

Periodic monitoring has mainly to do with the periodic tracking of pre-identified expected output and outcome indicators. As mentioned above, monitoring indicators need to be “developed and “owned” by each implementing organization as these indicators are specific to the GEP objectives, implemented measures and corresponding tasks/activities of each organization”. According to chapter 3 of the present methodology, different types of monitoring indicators can be identified: output indicators, short-term outcome indicators,

medium-term outcome indicators⁸. For each measure included in the GEP, partners will need to identify all types of indicators.

The identification of the indicators to be included in the plan should start from the ones already defined in the frame of the GEP design (T2.3) and included in the GEP itself. Further inputs can be obtained through the present methodology, as indeed examples of output and outcome indicators are provided from page 33 on of the present document and at Annex V, as well as under section 2.2 “Quantitative Indicators” of D1.1 “Internal and external Assessment Methodology and Guidelines”. They need to be adapted to the specific measures and activities described in the GEP.

Indicators should be monitored every four months following the formative evaluation cycles of paragraph 4.2. Concerning the methods to use to monitor output and outcome indicators, as visible in the table below, which is a part of the table of page 32 of the present document, a distinction has to be made between output and outcome indicators:

Evaluation Building Block		Methods	Sources
Targets & Indicators	Output (direct services, products or events produced by activities)	Documentary analysis	Intervention organizers.
	Outcome – Short-term (Post-test, pretest-post-test, etc.)	Polls, questionnaires, organizational statistics and indicators	Beneficiaries, participants
	Outcome – medium-term (Time-series)	Polls, questionnaires, interviews, organizational statistics and indicators	Beneficiaries, participants

Table 6: Indicators and methods for monitoring

According to the table, in order to track output indicators, data on participants have to be recorded along the implementation process, and related documents should be consulted (e.g. in order to track how many trainings have been organized or how many people have been engaged, it is necessary to consult the documentation elaborated in the frame of the specific activity), while for monitoring outcome indicators, the consultation of documents/records might not be enough, therefore other methods should be used such as polls, questionnaires, interviews etc.

4.3.2 Evaluation activities

As far as methods to be used within the evaluation activities are concerned, the following ones are recommended to be included in the plan:

- Documentary evidence/analysis, as recalled above;
- Focus groups;
- Semi-structured interviews;
- Questionnaires/polls.

Focus groups and semi-structured interviews are mainly meant at collecting qualitative data. **1 focus group and from 5 to 10 semi-structured interviews** should be organized in order to gather data related to the whole **implementation process**, by involving internal stakeholders engaged in the implementation (different from the

⁸ The explanation of the different types of indicators is provided at paragraph 3.2.7 of the present document.

GE WG members), while **1 dedicated focus group** should be organized for **each intervention/measure included in the GEP** by involving key actors, samples of beneficiaries and participants included.

For soft actions that concern the organization of initiatives (e.g. mentoring course, raising awareness activities, events, etc.) as an alternative to the focus group ad hoc questionnaires can be submitted to all participants (ex-post questionnaires). This would allow to gather more comprehensive feedback and data as well as to monitor indicators.

The table below summarizes the kind of evaluation activities that should be organized:

Evaluation activities	Methods	When
Single action/intervention	Questionnaires (especially for soft measures), focus groups (one per measure)	When the implementation of the specific action will be concluded
Overall implementation process	Interviews (from 5 to 7) and focus group (one)	M30, M44

Table 7: Summary of of evaluation activities

Examples of questions for focus groups, interviews and questionnaires are available in the monitoring and evaluation plan template.

Methodological guidance to carry out interviews and focus groups is available in “D1.1. Internal and External Assessment Methodologies and Guidelines” as well as Casillas et al. (2020), Bryman (2008) or other sources such as the [Oxfam Research Guidelines on Focus Groups](#).

4.3.3 Timeline

It is crucial to schedule the monitoring and evaluation activities in advance and to align them with the timeframe of the different actions that the institution is going to implement. When scheduling the monitoring and evaluation activities it is important to keep in mind that:

- Indicators should be monitored **every 4 months** according to the monitoring cycles indicated at page 37 and 38 of the present document;
- **Once the implementation of an action will be finalized**, a focus group should be organized involving key actors (including beneficiaries/participants) to evaluate the action. In case of actions consisting in initiatives such as mentoring course, raising awareness activities, events, etc., ad hoc ex-post questionnaires can be submitted to the participants, in addition or as an alternative to the focus group.
- **At the end of the first iteration phase**, one focus group involving internal stakeholders (not members of the GEP WG) and from 5 to 10 interviews should be organized in order to evaluate the whole implementation process.

4.4 Data collection tools

The monitoring and evaluation activities mentioned above must be reported using dedicate templates, linked or added as annexes in each partner’s Monitoring and evaluation plan. The outputs and outcome indicators will be collected through a dedicated spread sheet, whose template is available at the present [link](#)⁹. Concerning interviews, focus groups and questionnaires, instead, their results will be summarized and analyzed by each partner into an overall Formative evaluation report¹⁰ which template will be made available by Smart Venice in the forthcoming months, to feed into D4.2.

⁹ The file has to be downloaded. Partners cannot directly fill the file online.

¹⁰ The template will also include a part related to the evaluation of the design of the actions included in the GEP.

5 Summative Evaluation Methodology

The summative evaluation aims to determine the extent to which anticipated outcomes were produced by a given program or intervention. It will be carried out by **external, independent experts** towards the end of the Caliper project and will start in M30 and will finish in M48.

The following section specifies the methodological framework to be followed for each of the 9 implementing organizations. It provides clear indications for gathering evidence that can demonstrate the extent to which each of the implemented GEPs worked as intended and to which degree external factors have affected its outcomes and impact.

The **summative evaluation** (concerned with outputs, outcomes, and impact) **builds on the formative evaluation** described in the previous section. The formative evaluation examines and assesses the design and implementation of the GEPs and feeds into the summative evaluation – as design and implementation of GEP activities may begin to explain (or not) why certain outcomes and impacts are achieved. The summative evaluation will be based on on-site visits by the external evaluators and will comprised of the following methods: 5 x semi-structured interviews, 1 x focus group and 2 online questionnaires in each organization.

Measuring GEP outcomes and impacts is not a simple task. Firstly, the interplay between contextual factors, i.e. policy developments at a national or regional level and the intervention at the institutional level through a GEP are difficult to untangle when trying to explain how change has happened. This is even more complicated when the remit or scope of the GEP includes actions beyond the institutional level.

Assessing structural change for a greater gender equality in institutions can tap into various types of impact evaluation and assessment approaches which tend to revolve around different notions of causality (Rogers et al. 2015, 25). In the CALIPER evaluation framework, we aim to **demonstrate contribution**, i.e. examine whether or not the GEP has contributed to the observed change. Instead of making strong claims and identifying certain GEP actions as the unique, causal agent of change, the evaluation methodology focuses on the specific configurations of actions, actors and contextual factors that are likely to have affected the workplace.

Secondly, structural change is not a simple, straightforward process and there can be a considerable time lag between the GE activities and the generation of outcomes. Ideally, data needs to be collected over the long term so that meaningful and robust conclusions can be drawn. What data and how this data is collected, analyzed and the conclusions made from an analysis of this evidence depends on the specifics of what change is expected to happen. Of course, this needs to be tailored to and depends on the identified measures of each specific GEP.

5.1 Assessment of GEP outcomes and impact

5.1.1 Related WP tasks and resources

Assessing the outcomes and impacts of the implementation of the GEPs is a key component of the project and is specifically related to D1.2 Internal Gender Equality Assessment Results as well as Task 2.3 GEPs design and development.

It also builds on the **internal formative evaluation** which is carried out in Task 4.2. The report from the 2nd round of formative evaluation will be available in M46 and provide valuable input for the summative evaluation. It will

- compare the design analysis (log-frame template) to the observed outcomes and impacts
- build on the implementation analysis to explain how (or how not) certain outcomes and impacts have been achieved

5.1.2 Theoretical assumptions and available evidence

Various types of measures have been developed through GEPs by various research performing and research funding organizations and this is accompanied by a **range of evidence as to their effectiveness**.

The typology of actions and their corresponding impact indicators are described from page 14ff of D1.1. of the Caliper project. CALIPER like all institutional change projects responds to the three gender equality and gender mainstreaming priorities defined by the European Commission: 1) removing institutionalized gendered barriers to careers; (2) promoting gender equality in decision-making and (3) integrating the gender dimension into research content and teaching.

The following examples regarding the impact of certain measures is not meant to be exhaustive but illustrate how data can be gathered to demonstrate outcomes and impacts of a range of different types of measures that have been implemented in RPOs/RFOs.

Removing gender-related institutional barriers to careers

For example, the Irish Research Council carried out gender blinding for assessments in early-stage career research programs – this means that its assessors review applications that are anonymous and free from pronouns or other words that would identify the applicant's gender. Data collected and analyzed by the Irish Research Council demonstrates the impact of the policy: women made up only 35% of STEM postdoctoral awards in 2013 – rising to 44% in 2014 and to 45% in 2015. Data gathered also demonstrates how in 2013 female STEM researchers submitted 43% of postdoctoral applications yet won only 35% of the awards. The implementation of the gender blind assessment saw the almost reversal of these figures: women applying for the 2014 STEM postdoctoral fellowships submitted 32% of applications yet went on to win 44% (Irish Research Council, 2016:3).

As regarding grant allocation for early career researchers – the Science Foundation Ireland developed a Starting investigator research Grant (SirG) award programme which ensured that 50% of eligible applicants are women. This saw the increase of women applicants from 27% in 2013 to 21% in 2015. The usual peer review process remained unchanged but – of the 20 proposals awarded in 2015, 55% were women compared to 27% in 2013 (Science Europe, 2017:30).

Addressing gender balance in decision-making

Addressing gender balance in decision-making is also another common area for intervention and does not only refer to the equal presence of women and men in all relevant boards and committees but also refers to the ability of their members to address their own biases and make informed decisions (Oetke, et al 2016). This can be done by developing measures that ensure that all bodies are gender-sensitive and aware. Regarding a balanced representation – Ghent University in Belgium developed election rules requiring faculties to have at least one male and one female candidate for the elections. If the elections have an unbalanced gender outcome (i.e. not respecting the minimum 40/60 gender balance) the candidate with the least votes from the overrepresented sex (compared to other faculties) has to give way to the faculty's candidate of the other sex with the highest number of votes. The new procedures contributed to a 50/50 composition in 2014 (EIGE, 2016:12).

The gender-integrated leadership programme (AKKA) at the Lund University (Sweden) is a programme whereby leadership for structural change is understood as something that can be learnt and developed, and that focuses on the individual's competences, and not on personal characteristics.

TO KNOW MORE

“The AKKA programme aims at raising gender knowledge and awareness, and providing methods and tools for structural change in order to achieve sustainable gender equality. From 2004 to 2014, five AKKA programmes have been offered for 150 senior scholars in Lund University (Sweden) (of which 37

were men). The programme runs over a year with monthly meetings. Throughout the years, AKKA has increased the number of women in leading positions, contributed to an enhanced visibility of women as potential leaders, increased willingness of both women and men to assume leadership positions, raised gender awareness among female and male academic leaders, promoted networking and collaboration within the university, raised the knowledge about the university's politics and activities, developed tools to deal with resistance to gender issues and for change management, contributed to highlight discrimination, and developed concrete change projects." (EIGE, 2016, 46)

Integrating the gender dimension into research content

Integrating the gender dimension into education and research content is another area for intervention. Different RPOs, including universities and research institutes and RFOs have employed various strategies and interventions to ensure that the gender dimension is suitably integrated in curricular and research projects.

A research funder in Austria created a funding programme for projects integrating the gender dimension in research content. The calls address technology-intensive companies, non-university research organisations, universities and universities of applied sciences. It initiates gender-sensitive projects in research, technology and innovation to develop tailor-made, innovative solutions. FEMtech Research Projects promotes the implementation of gender throughout various stages of the research design, beginning with the research question, through data collection, data analysis and documentation. Tenders are open to all topics in the area of applied research, technology/product/process development, as well as usability studies, environmental analyses and feasibility studies. Wroblewski states "Ideally, the thorough implementation of gender can lead to three impacts; firstly, giving gender a better standing in non-university research, secondly, raising awareness for the relevance of gender in research and lastly, improving the quality of the research projects' results" (Wroblewski, 2016a, p.27). Not only further research but another impact was linked to the better quality of proposals. Some interviewees identified that they could improve the scientific quality of the gender part of research proposals in other funding schemes.

Raising awareness of gender issues

One of the main areas to address, whilst managing institutional change is raising awareness of gender issues, this includes tackling denial and resistance to change as well as promoting a process of self reflection for top-management and different actors (e.g. RPO managers with responsibility for human resources and career advancement; RFO managers with responsibility for establishing funding criteria; selection, promotion and evaluation committees) to recognise and eliminate sources of gender bias. Gender stereotypes and biases are deeply embedded in our unconscious and can affect how we behave and interact with others. Research has demonstrated how unconscious or implicit gender bias means that women are more negatively assessed than men for the same job or achievement because they are less likely to be associated with stereotypical male characteristics which are perceived as necessary for success (Science Europe, 2017: 12-13). Action related to gender awareness and bias should be combined with non-discriminatory policies in order to foster an inclusive culture and work environment -addressing gender as well as other grounds of discrimination (TARGET, 2018:15).

5.1.3 Target Audience

Each RPO/ RFO is comprised of a range of relevant stakeholders. Specific interventions of a GEP might address different target audiences, including:

Top-management

- Rectors and Vice Rectors
- Institutional Heads
- Director General/ Board

Middle-management

- Human Resource Managers

- Deans
- Faculty heads
- Programme Managers
- Information Systems Managers

Staff

- Researchers
- Academics
- Administrators
- Technicians
- Gender Equality Officers
- Communications staff

Students

Other decision-making bodies such as workers council, trade- or student unions.

The summative evaluation for each of the 9 implementing institutions will specify the relevant target audiences implied – as indicated in the corresponding GEP documents.

5.1.4 Goals & Activities

The specific goals and activities of each RPO/ RFO will be extracted from the corresponding GEP and formative evaluation reports.

5.1.5 Evaluation Priorities

The CALIPER summative evaluation of the GEP regarding its outputs, outcomes and impacts at the institutional level has the following priorities:

Evaluate the extent to which implementing institutions have fostered institutional change by

- Assessing the extent to which expected outcomes and impacts have been achieved in each of the implementing institutions
- Identifying the main outputs, outcomes and impacts of the GEPs in terms of both gender equality and R&I (intended and unintended) in each implementing institutions
- Assessing the extent to which awareness of gender issues and institutional actions/ policies has been raised
- Assessing the extent to which the scope of the GEP has expanded to other institutions/ departments within the organization

5.1.6 Methods and Instruments

The CALIPER summative evaluation of the GEP will focus on objective and tangible outcomes and impacts, beyond potentially biased perceptions of positive impact from actively involved stakeholders. It will be based on the self-assessment formative evaluation as mentioned as well as 1 site-visit per implementing institution, involving focus groups and semi-structured interviews. In addition, an online questionnaire will be used.

Institutional OOI Online Questionnaire

The summative evaluation will carry out a total of two online surveys. The first one gathers information

regarding progress on institutional GE policies and experiences, while the second (described under section 3.2.7 on page 51) targets the R&I Innovation Hubs.

An institutional online questionnaire will be widely disseminated to staff and students to gauge the levels of awareness of both gender issues and those policies/ actions developed at the institutional level. It will be developed and implemented online by the external evaluator and will widely publicized by the GEP WGs of the implementing institutions. It will build on the Gender Equality Audit and Monitoring tool (GEAM tool) developed through the ACT project which provides an integrated environment for carrying out survey-based gender equality audits in organizations (e.g. university or research performing organization) or organizational units (faculty, departments).

The GEAM comprises many different questionnaire modules which will be examined and customized in the light of the initial audit carried out by each implementing organization as described in D1.1. of the Caliper project.

Beyond the GEAM, the questionnaire will also incorporate a specific section on the analysis of the external partner collaborations in the wider ecosystem.

Onsite study visits

The summative evaluation includes onsite study visits of each of the 9 implementing organizations. These will consist of 1-2 day visits, that provide the opportunity to get to know involved members of the WGs, administrative staff and representatives of the scientific management as well other stakeholders. During the onsite visits the semi-structured interviews as well as the focus groups will be held.

In addition, first hand experiences regarding the location of the campus (buildings) and/or building, information display, or even (child) care facilities can be obtained. On-site visits also enable to get an understanding of workplace layouts, community and/or recreational facilities.

Institution	Country/City	Scheduled
Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computing of University of Zagreb	Zagreb, Croatia	
Yaşar University	İzmir, Turkey	
University of Salento	Lecce, Italy	
IRB Barcelona	Barcelona, Spain	
National Technical University of Athens	Athens, Greece	
Université libre de Bruxelles	Brussels, Belgium	
The Slovak University of Technology	Bratislava, Slovakia	
Shota Rustaveli National Science Foundation	Tbilisi, Georgia	
Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding	Bucharest, Romania	

Table 8: On-site visits schedule

Semi-structured interviews

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

Three semi-structured interviews will be carried in each implementing institution with different representatives. These should represent different levels of hierarchy within the institution – including GEP WG members. Ideally these would include one representative from top management one member from middle management (decision-makers) and one staff member.

Implementing Organization	Organizational Position	Interviews
RPO 1	Top Management	1
RPO 1	Middle management	1
RPO 1	Employee / Staff	1
Total		3

Table 9: Interviews planning

Interview Question Guide:

Thematic Block 1:

- Identify the main outputs, outcomes and impacts of the GEPs in terms of both gender equality and R&I (intended and unintended) in each implementing institutions

Thematic Block 2:

- Assess the extent to which expected outcomes and impacts have been achieved in each of the implementing institutions
- Identify facilitating and hindering factors (context) for achieving outcomes and impacts

Thematic Block 3:

- Assess the extent to which the scope of the GEP has expanded to other institutions/ departments within the organization
- Successful and not-so successful strategies

Together with the 7 semi-structured interviews carried out as part of the self-assessment process, the overall evaluation will be based upon a total of 10 interviews per implementing institution.

5.2 Assessment of Caliper R&I Hubs and Innovation Ecosystem

An important second part of the summative evaluation consists of the assessment of the “innovation ecosystem” approach pursued by Caliper. R&I Hubs with Quadruple Helix stakeholders will be set up with the goal of strengthening the relevance of the intra-organizational GEP design and taking advantage of spill-over effects across regional actors.

5.2.1 Related WP tasks and resources

The relevant work package descriptions specifying the involvement of Quadruple Helix stakeholders in Caliper are given in WP2, Task 2.2 on the “Organization of Multi-stakeholder Dialogues” and in WP5, Task 5.2 “Engaging with the Innovation Ecosystem”.

Preparatory work is carried out during WP1 Task 1.4 regarding the “external framework conditions and innovation ecosystems from a gender perspective”. This report provides the analysis of the wider policy context, including the hindering and facilitating context factors.

The summative evaluation will build upon “D1.3 Gender Analysis of Research and Innovation Ecosystem” of each implementing partner. The report will analyze the national legal and policy framework as well as the network of stakeholders of the national and regional innovation ecosystem.

It will also build upon certain formative evaluation activities carried such as posttest surveys of implemented events as well as produced reports (of events) or meeting minutes.

5.2.2 Theoretical assumptions and available evidence

The project pursues an ambitious agenda by conceiving the development and implementation of intra-organizational GEPs in the context of the wider regional and national innovation ecosystem. Such an approach is based on empirical data and scientific literature identified in T1.3 and T1.4. Situating the “innovation ecosystem” approach within the wider scientific literature is important in order to contextualize and contrast the obtained results with a wider range of empirical evidence.

Overall, taking a broader extra-organizational perspective on GEPs makes intuitively sense as universities and research organizations form part of a regional and national “Quadruple Helix” ecosystem composed of key actors from industry & business, the public sector and government, or civil society organizations. Many of the problems addressed within academic organizations in relation to gender equality are directly or indirectly conditioned by the wider innovation ecosystem, such as the influx of students, labor market regulations, available funding, or entrepreneurial opportunities for R&D related spin-offs.

By focusing on the regional level, different actors can take advantage basically of two things (Spigel 2017): first, the shared cultural understandings within the different regions that eases knowledge sharing and exchange of human resources. Since local actors have an intimate knowledge regarding the status quo of the complex relationships between cultural, social, economic and political actors, a regional approach facilitates institutional change that is of societal and economic relevance. Second, the (existing) networks among stakeholders also facilitate spillovers in terms of firms and universities, entrepreneurial opportunity, and available capital investment. By addressing the wider extra-organizational context, GEP actions within organizations therefore not only can gain in visibility, legitimacy or support but also generate spill-over effects between different organizations and sectors that can function as a driver for organization-internal change processes.

This ecosystem-oriented approach of Caliper is clearly an innovative feature of the project, as most previous structural change projects focus exclusively on organizational change processes without engaging systematically with the already mentioned four types of stakeholders that comprise the Quadruple Helix approach. The project echoes implicitly the important insight from network analysis, that the relations in which actors are embedded in are key in shaping their behavior. However, while such a systemic approach to organizational change is ambitious and innovative, it also is risky out of several reasons.

First, GEP implementation within a single organization is a complex and resource intensive process by itself. By stretching project- and human resources towards an entire region, coordination efforts might become unsustainable and workloads unmanageable. The available resources might be insufficient with efforts too dispersed to have any impact – inside the organization and beyond. In this regard, it will be key to analyze the degree with which partner organizations are able to build upon existing Quadruple Helix cooperation or would need to build-up such networks within their region from scratch.

Second, the awareness of “gender issues” within the academic triple and quadruple helix literature is scarce, let alone among many of the implied empirical actors in general. As we know through the literature, especially among technologically oriented companies or among entrepreneurs in general, women are usually under-represented while gender issues are seldom a priority. As the literature on gender and entrepreneurship ecosystems has shown, women are generally disadvantaged (Brush et al. 2019). Several publications also have emphasized the gendered nature of “innovation” and “innovation policy” (Alsos, Ljunggren, and Hytti 2013; Blake and Hanson 2005). Although the role of civil society actors as facilitators of new and hitherto marginalized

forms of innovation has been remarked (Lindberg, Lindgren, and Packendorff 2014; Lindberg, Danilda, and Torstensson 2011), the probable “gender-blindness” of most Quadruple Helix actors poses a challenge to tap into “spill-over” effects among actors regarding a specific, shared gender equality agenda. This is especially true for Eastern European countries where the engagement with gender issues has traditionally been less thorough as for example compared to northern European countries.

Given this wider context regarding the potential strength and challenges regarding a ecosystem oriented approach to GEP implementation, the proposed evaluation will concentrate on the following audiences, goals, activities, indicators and instruments.

5.2.3 Audiences

The innovation ecosystem comprises a diverse set of stakeholders. Following the Quadruple Helix approach, the overarching stakeholder categories are academic organizations, industry and business, government and public sector as well as civil society. Each category in turn can contain a quite diverse set of actors in terms of their roles and goals.

Academia and universities

- Schools of applied science
- Research and innovation centers with strong industry links (e.g. Fraunhofer in Germany)
- Universities
- Schools of professional and vocational training

Government and public sector

- Schools
- Quality assurance agencies for the academic sector
- Business and employment agencies, regulation
- City councils

Industry and business

- Start-ups
- SME's
- Multinational, large scale corporations

Civil Society

- Citizen science initiatives, Fablabs,
- Women's NGOs
- Girls for STEM initiatives

Deliverable D1.3 provides a more detailed and empirical overview of the diverse stakeholders that comprise the 9 innovation ecosystems.

5.2.4 Goals

- Setup of Caliper Research & Innovation Hubs (T2.2)
 - Identify shared/key challenges that influence GEP design and development
 - Develop portfolio of strategic priorities
 - Raise awareness of top and middle management awareness of how gender equality can contribute to excellence and innovation in a network context
- Engage with the Innovation Ecosystem, FemTech Events (T5.2)

- Create strong links between GEP and stakeholders of the innovation ecosystem
- raise awareness and highlight women led innovations, gender sensitive product development
- attract more girls to STEM
- facilitate mobility of women researchers from/to academia and business sector.
- Sustainability (T5.4)
 - GE initiatives for starting internal work to promote structural change in external R&I Hub members
 - Development Charter on Institutional Change for Gender Equal Research and Innovation Hub

5.2.5 Activities

The relevant tasks and activities in relation to the innovation ecosystem are the following:

T2.2. Organization of Multistakeholder Dialogues

- 2 dialog workshops at each RPO/RFO (18 in total) involving Quadruple Helix actors

T5.2 Engaging with Innovation Ecosystem

- 1 joint FemTech event at each RPO/RFO (9 in total) involving Quadruple Helix actors

T5.4 Sustainability

- 2 GE webinars at each RPO/RFO (18 in total) (min. 80 RPO/RFO involved)

5.2.6 Evaluation priorities

Given the overall audiences, objectives and activities, the Caliper summative evaluation of the innovation ecosystem approach has the following priorities:

- assess the overall creation of 9 R&I Hubs (one for each of the partner regions) and the overall state of collaboration among participants across the four Quadruple Helix sectors.
- assess to which degree a shared agenda and shared priorities on gender equality among the innovation ecosystem stakeholders has been established
- identify challenges and synergies of collaboration among participating Quadruple Helix stakeholders
- assess the influence and contribution of R&I Hubs to intra-organizational GEP design and implementation
- assess the level of awareness raising regarding the importance of gender for research and innovation activities across the Quadruple Helix
- assess the contribution of the innovation ecosystem approach to sustainability of Caliper outcomes; synergistic effects.

5.2.7 Methods & Instruments

In order to assess the overall outcomes (short-term, medium-term) and (long-term) impact of innovation ecosystem activities, the following indicators and research instruments will be used.

The summative evaluation will build upon the formative evaluation of innovation ecosystem relevant activities. This may include posttest assessment of workshops, events and webinars, specified in the section on formative

evaluation.

Objective	Activity	Goals	Instruments
Creation of R&I Hubs	9 x 2 dialog workshops	Network of collaborating Quadruple Helix stakeholders (Short-term outcome)	Post-workshop evaluation Online questionnaire Focus Group
		Shared agenda and priorities (medium-term outcome)	Workshop minutes/reports Focus Group
		Awareness raising on gender issues (medium-term outcome)	Online questionnaire Focus Group
Engage with Innovation Ecosystem	9 x 1 FemTech event	Create (strong) links among R&I Hub participants (Short/medium-term outcome)	Post-event evaluation Online questionnaire Focus Group
		Raise awareness on gender issues (medium-term outcome)	Online questionnaire Focus Group
		Attract more girls to STEM (Long-term impact)	Monitoring of % of female students among different university degrees/courses
		Facilitate mobility of human resources across sectors (Long-term impact)	
Sustainability of GE measures	9 x 2 webinars	GE activities in Quadruple Helix partner organizations	Focus Group Online questionnaire
		Caliper Charter	

Table 10: Activities and tasks carried out as part of the overall Caliper Ecosystem engagement

Post-test surveys (part of formative evaluation)

The formative evaluation will specify posttest questionnaires to be distributed among participants of dialog workshops, FemTech events and webinars. These evaluation questionnaires are usually distributed towards the end of the events. The literature contends that evaluations are usually biased in favor of a positive assessment of the activities. They are also limited to assess the mid-range outcomes mainly and not long-term impact. Nevertheless, they provide valid information and often suggestions for improving future events.

Semi-structured Interviews

The semi-structured interviews to be carried out in each implementing institution will incorporate a specific thematic section regarding the collaboration with external stakeholders. For the evaluation of the R&I Hubs, not additional interviews are foreseen other than those already specified for the summative evaluation under section 3.1.2 on page 42.

Thematic Block 1: Scope and nature of collaboration among Quadruple Helix stakeholders

- Name collaborators (identify sector of each), their role and frequency of collaboration.
- Qualitative assessment and character of collaboration (strength of ties, trust, cooperation, etc.)

- Identify main interest and agenda of collaboration (shared interest/domain)

Thematic Block 2: Benefits, challenges, obstacles

- Successful and unsuccessful initiatives for contact and communication
- Anchorage, synergies and drivers from the ecosystem towards organizational internal processes.

Thematic Block 3: Gender awareness

- Probe understandings of innovation and entrepreneurship; example of successful innovation, example of unsuccessful innovation
- Visibility of women entrepreneurs, innovators. Awareness of gender issues and gender knowledge

Online R&I Hub Questionnaire

A second online survey carried out during the summative evaluation will assess the scope and health of the R&I Hubs.¹¹ As the number of interviews is limited, the evaluation will deploy an online questionnaire in order to obtain a more complete picture of the extent and nature of established collaboration among Quadruple Helix stakeholders.

This task will build upon the initial mapping of the respective, local innovation ecosystem (as described in D1.3). However, instead of mapping the entire network of collaborations (as done for D1.3), the evaluation methodology will focus on the participants of the R&I Hubs solely, not addressing all actors within the regional innovation ecosystem that do not participate in the Caliper activities in a narrower sense. The target audience therefore also clearly differs from the institutional level questionnaire which targets staff/employees of the implementing organization.

Information provided by lead partners of each of the 9 R&I Hubs, participant list of the (a) dialogue workshops, (b) FemTech events, and (c) online seminars as well as specific questions regarding collaboration partners during the semi-structured interviews will identify most important actors.

Based upon this initial listing of R&I Hub participants, a roster will be generated asking respondents to rate/interpret the provided names (in terms of frequency and strength of the relation). The survey will also provide space for additional positions within each actors networks using a “resource generator” methodology¹².

In addition, the survey will inquire about the health of the overall collaboration among R&I Hub participants. An adapted version of the Wilders Collaboration Factors Inventory (Mattessich, Murray-Close, and Monsey 2001)¹³ will be used. The Wilders Inventory is a 20-items strong questionnaire to assess the “health” and development success of a collaboration network. It includes items regarding shared vision, trust and mutual respect among group members, leadership, distribution of roles, or appropriate pacing among others. The Wilders measurement scale is widely used for assessing participants’ engagement in collaborations (Fraser et al. 2017), creating sound measures by which to compare projects. Small adjustments will be made to adapt the questionnaire to the specific context of the R&I Hubs.

¹¹The first survey targets – as described under section 3.1.6 on page 44. experiences and progress of institutional policies.

¹²A “resource generator” is a data collection tool used in social network analysis to ask respondents about access to specific resources via person/contacts. Thus, a typical question used in a resource generator would be “To whom do you turn for support regarding unforeseen care emergencies”.

¹³ See also <http://bit.ly/2wBUaxD>

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Annex I: Evaluation Component Overview

		Key Evaluation Questions	Methods	Tools	Responsibilities
	GEP	Please state the scope of GEP coverage (identified unit, institution, department, whole organization) and the period of time it covers (start date/ end date)	Documentary evidence (web-site/ relevant reports/literature, GEP),	Formative Evaluation Template	
FORMATIVE EVALUATION	Design	Describe the history of the GEP, have there been predecessors?	Documentary evidence (web-site/ relevant reports/literature, GEP),	Formative Evaluation Template	External Evaluator -Develop the Evaluation Methodology -Develop Formative/ Summative Evaluation Template - Develop Focus Group guide
		What are the relevant policy context factors that hinder/ facilitate the GEP? GE/ R&I	National policy reports , EU level reports, relevant literarture.	Fill in design/ concpet analysis.	
		What are the relevant organisational context factors that hinder/ facilitate the GEP? GE/ R&I	Institutional policy documents .	Fill in design/ concpet analysis.	
		Who are the main target groups?	Documentary evidence (GEP, web-site/ relevant reports/literature/ s ,),	Fill in design/ concpet analysis.	SMART Venice & VIL -Give training on the Formative Evaluation Methodology -Facilitate 1 x Focus Group per implementing institution -Provide support for each institution to fill in formative evaluation template
		Aims and objectives: What outcomes (short and medium term) and impacts (long term) are expected? Are these only related to GE or also to R&I?	Documentary evidence (GEP, web-site/ relevant reports/ literature) Focus Group	-Formative Evaluation Template -Fill in design/ concpet analysis.	
		Are targets and indicators specified? If so, what are these?	GEP	Formative Evaluation Template	
		What are the main activities?	Documentary evidence (GEP, web-site/	Fill in design/ concpet	
					Implementing Institutions (II) - Give feedback on Evaluation

		Key Evaluation Questions	Methods	Tools	Responsibilities
			relevant reports/ literature/)	analysis.	Methodology Version 1
		What resources are available for the intervention? (Specify: HR, financial, time, etc.)	Documentary evidence (GEP, web-site/ relevant reports/literature/) Focus Group	Formative Evaluation Template	- Participate in 1 x Focus Group - Carry out 7 x semi-structured interviews -Fill in Formative Evaluation Template & Log Frame for each intervention
		Elaborate its design: How should it work? Step by step	Documentary evidence (GEP, web-site/ relevant reports/ literature) Focus Group	Formative Evaluation Template Fill in log-frame template	
		Validity of design: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explanation of design process • Is it logical and realistic? 	Documentary evidence (GEP, web-site/ relevant reports/ literature) Focus Group	Formative Evaluation Template	
		Who are the key institutional players?	Documentary evidence (GEP, web-site/ relevant reports/literature) Focus Group	-Formative Evaluation Template	
		Significance of GEP e.g. are core underlying problems addressed, do planned activities imply a significant change relative to existing institutional settings, do they fit with overall agendas, strategies.	Documentary evidence (GEP, web-site/ relevant reports/literature) Focus Group	-Formative Evaluation Template	

		Key Evaluation Questions	Methods	Tools	Responsibilities
		<p>Can the objectives be fulfilled – given the amount of resources?</p> <p>-is the allocation of financial and personnel resources to implement the GEP adequate?</p> <p>-are targets/goals realistic?</p>	<p>Documentary evidence (GEP, web-site/ relevant reports/literature)</p> <p>Focus Group</p>	-Formative Evaluation Template	
	Implementation Analysis:	Does the implementation of the GEP correspond to the objectives?	<p>Documentary evidence (GEP, web-site/ relevant reports/literature)</p> <p>Focus Group</p>	Formative Evaluation Template	
		To what extent has implementation changed over time? What has changed?	<p>Documentary evidence (GEP, web-site/ relevant reports/literature)</p> <p>Focus Group</p>	Formative Evaluation Template	
		How are the responsibilities for the implementation of the GEP distributed?	<p>Documentary evidence (GEP, web-site/ relevant reports/literature)</p> <p>Focus Group</p>	Formative Evaluation Template	
		What are the main decision-making bodies involved with the implementation of the GEP? Is there a commitment from top-level decision-making bodies?	<p>Documentary evidence (GEP, web-site/ relevant reports/literature)</p> <p>Focus Group</p>	Formative Evaluation Template	
		Have any institutional bodies or mechanisms been established to implement the GEP?	<p>Documentary evidence (GEP, web-site/ relevant reports/literature)</p> <p>Focus Group</p>	Formative Evaluation Template	
		What factors inhibit or promote the implementation of the GEP in line with	<p>Documentary evidence (GEP, web-site/ relevant reports/literature)</p>	Formative Evaluation Template	

		Key Evaluation Questions	Methods	Tools	Responsibilities
		its objectives?	Focus Group		
		What barriers were encountered during the implementation? Was it possible to overcome these barriers and how?	Documentary evidence (GEP, web-site/ relevant reports/literature) Focus Group		
SUMMATIVE EVALUATION	Impact Assessment	What are the main short-term outcomes of the GEP that can be observed? (GE & R&I) Do these coincide with the expected outputs? How are these measured?	Institutional OOI Online Questionnaire Documentary evidence (web-site/ relevant reports/literature, Formative Evaluation Report) Interviews	Summative Evaluation Template	External Evaluator: On-site visits 3 x semi-structure interviews per institution 1 x focus group
		What are the main medium-term outcomes of the intervention (per target group) (GE & R&I) that can be observed? Do these coincide with the expected outcomes? How are these measured?	Institutional OOI Online Questionnaire Documentary evidence (web-site/ relevant reports/literature, Formative Evaluation Report) Interviews	Summative Evaluation Template	Develop 2 x Online Questionnaires - Institutional OOIs - R&I Hubs Analyse results of 2 x questionnaires, 3 x interviews, 1 focus group. Develop Summative Report Template
		What (type of) main impacts (indirect/direct, intended/unintended/ GE & R&I) of the intervention can be observed? Do these coincide with expected impacts? How are these measured?	Institutional OOI Online Questionnaire Documentary evidence (web-site/ relevant reports/literature, Formative Evaluation Report) Interviews	Summative Evaluation Template	Collate all Summative Evaluations into one report Implementing Institutions -Publicize the OOI / R&I Hub

		Key Evaluation Questions	Methods	Tools	Responsibilities
		How sustainable are these?			questionnaires
		To what extent has the intervention becomes embedded into institutional routine/ regulations/ processes?			-Participate in interviews & focus groups
		To what extent is there an increased awareness of gender issues and institutional actions for gender equality?	Institutional OOI Online Questionnaire		-Implement post-workshop/event evaluation
		To what extent has the scope of the GEP expanded to other institutions / departments within the organisation?	Institutional OOI Online Questionnaire Documentary evidence (GEP, web-site/ relevant reports/literature) Interviews	Summative Evaluation Template	-Facilitate information to external evaluator
		What is the scope and nature of collaboration among Quadruple Helix Stakeholders? What are the benefits, challenges and obstacles of a quadruple helix approach to GEPs?	Quadruple Helix Questionnaire Interviews Post-workshop/event evaluation	Summative Evaluation Template	
		To what extent has gender awareness been promoted as part of the quadruple helix approach?			

Annex II: Caliper Formative Evaluation Templates / Questions

The following formative evaluation templates are included in this document to help each implementing institution to gather the relevant information needed for their self-assessment. Corresponding to the overall approach, there are two evaluation templates: a first one for evaluating the design of the GEP and a second template for carrying out the implementation analysis.

In each case, please make sure to reference the available evidence adequately. This concerns documentary evidence (e.g. strategy plans or official statements published by the organization) as well as material recollected during the evaluation such as interview or focus group transcripts.

Design Analysis

Please use the following questions together with the design template on page 17 to generate a log-frame for each intervention measure to be implemented.

1. Design analysis
1.1 Please state the scope of GEP coverage (identified unit, institution, department, whole organization) and the period of time it covers (start date/ end date)
1.2. Describe the history of the intervention, have there been predecessors?
1.3 What are the relevant policy context factors that hinder/ facilitate this intervention? GE/ R&I
1.4 What are the relevant organization context factors that hinder/ facilitate this intervention? GE/ R&I
1.5 Which different types of actors from the local research and innovation eco-system collaborate in this intervention?
1.6 Who are the main target groups?
1.7 Goals and objectives: What outcomes (short and medium term) and impacts (long term) are expected? (GE and R&I)
1.8. Are targets and indicators specified? If so, what are these?
1.9 What are the main activities?
1.10. What resources are available for the intervention? (Specify: HR, financial, time, etc.)
1.11. Elaborate its design: How should it work? Step by step
1.12. Validity of design: Explanation of design process, is it logical and realistic?
1.13. Who are the key institutional players?
1.14. Significance of intervention e.g. are core underlying problems addressed? Do planned activities imply a significant change relative to existing institutional settings, do they fit with overall agendas, strategies?
1.15 Can the objectives be fulfilled – given the amount of resources? Is the allocation of financial and

personnel resources to implement the intervention adequate? Are targets/ goals realistic?

Implementation Analysis

Ideally, an excel file is used to monitor the key dimensions of the implemented activities for each measure. The key dimensions are listed in the implementation template on page 29.

2. Implementation analysis
2.1 Does the implementation of the intervention correspond to the objectives?
2.2 Have activities been carried out as foreseen? List the short-term and medium-term outcome indicator for each activity.
2.4. To what extent has implementation changed over time? What has changed?
2.5. How are responsibilities for the implementation of the intervention distributed?
2.6. What are the main decision making bodies involved with the implementation of the GEP? Is there a commitment from top-level decision-making bodies?
2.7. Have any institutional bodies or mechanisms been established to implement the intervention?
2.8. What factors inhibit or promote the implementation of the intervention in line with its objectives?
2.9. What barriers were encountered during the implementation? Was it possible to overcome these barriers and how?
2.10 Which external actors / influencing stakeholders have been involved?

References

CALIPER Deliverables
Interviews:
Monitoring Reports:
Evaluation Reports:
Other Reports:

Academic literature:
Websites:

Annex III: CALIPER Summative Evaluation Template - Questions

3. Impact Assessment
3.1. What are the main outputs of the GEP that can be observed (GE and R&I)? Do these coincide with the expected outputs? How are these measured?
3.2. What are the main outcomes (per target group) (GE & R&I) that can be observed? Do these coincide with the expected outcomes? How are these measured?
3.3. What (type of) main impacts (indirect/ direct, intended/ unintended/ GE& R&I) of the intervention can be observed? Do these coincide with expected impacts? How are these measured? How sustainable are these impacts?
3.4 To what extent has the intervention becomes embedded into institutional routine/ regulations/ processes?
3.5 To what extent is there an increased awareness of gender issues and institutional actions for gender equality?
3.6 To what extent has the scope of the GEP expanded to other institutions/ departments within the organisation?
3.7 What is the scope and nature of collaboration among Quadruple Helix stakeholders?
3.8 What are the benefits, challenges and obstacles of a quadruple helix approach to GEPs?
3.9 To what extent has gender awareness been promoted as part of the quadruple helix approach?
3.10 What are the main factors that have hindered/ supported the impacts of the intervention?

Annex IV: Example Gender Equality Plan Measures

Dimension	Field of Action	Sub-field of action	Measure
Removing gender-related institutional barriers to careers	Gender inclusive organizational culture	Gender awareness and bias	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Implicit bias training Gender-awareness training Diversity training Appeal body – HR Representatives, GE Officer Gender sensitive communication Incorporate implicit bias statements
		Non-discrimination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Zero-tolerance sexual harassment policies Equal treatment of part-time work and promotion of work-life balance Fair and transparent workload balance across all areas (teaching, research, administration) Equal access to resources (e.g. funding, lab space, equipment) Policies of overall non-discrimination
	Presence	Recruitment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Transparency of selection processes Gender sensitive formulation of advertisements for open position; publications of adverts in wide-spectrum of outlets Promotion of non-discriminatory hiring/ admission practices (e.g. anonymized applications) Gender balanced/ gender trained hiring committees Targeted recruitment
		Retention and attrition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training of HR managers Mobility rules and policies of outside hiring Career/professional development options Policies to reduce pay gap Policies to increase job security Analysis of attrition at all levels of career and its causes Develop mentoring program
		Advancement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Balanced women's representation in promotion pools Balanced women's representation in application pools for grant awards Promotion policies and practices (e.g. the possibility of stopping the tenure clock at universities due to parental leave or family leave) Targets for grant award holders Gender as a criterion for ranking applications Gender balanced evaluation panels for grant award Flexible grant management practices, e.g. in parental and family leaves
	Flexibility, time and	Work-life balance	Reasonable working hours, limited overtime and holiday and vacation policies

Dimension	Field of Action	Sub-field of action	Measure
	work-life	Care & Family Life	<p>Avoidance of environments that foster the creation of “Old boys clubs” (e.g. meetings held late in the evening)</p> <p>Measures addressing the pressure created by the myth of dedication being equal to time to spend</p> <p>Availability and equal treatment of part-time positions</p> <p>Child care availability and funding tailored to researchers’ needs</p> <p>parental leaves: “father quota”</p> <p>Carer/ parent-friendly workplaces (e.g. breastfeeding rooms, ‘with child offices’, breaks)</p> <p>Support of the ‘dual-earner’/ ‘dual carer’ family model</p> <p>Non-discrimination of parents</p> <p>Provision of interim technical or administrative support during a leave of absence related to care giving responsibilities</p> <p>Family friendly grant management practices (for example, direct measures to support maternity and paternity leave; support for paternity leave for dual career couples; support to switch from a full-time grant to a part-time grant or extending the grant at no cost</p>
Decision-making	Addressing gender bias in decision-making		<p>Introducing gender balance (40%/60%) or gender quotas in boards, bodies and committees</p> <p>Develop election rules to foster a balanced gender composition</p> <p>Ensuring that all bodies are gender-sensitive and aware</p>
Gender dimension	Gender dimension in education		<p>Mainstreaming gender awareness in all curriculum</p> <p>Including methods of sex and gender analysis and related knowledge in all curricula</p> <p>Developing new knowledge and training methods for students and researchers in fields where sex and gender analysis is of special relevance</p> <p>Collecting and publicizing research that has successfully integrated sex and / or gender perspectives.</p>
	Gender dimension in research content		<p>Asking research applicants to address ‘how sex and gender analysis is taken into account in the project’s content’</p> <p>Raising gender awareness and competence for applicants, reviewers or evaluation panels, providing specific guidance and training</p> <p>Providing tools for researchers to understand and apply gender in research content methods in their research fields, for instance through training, workshops, seminars or showcasing good examples</p> <p>Creating incentives for researchers to consider methods of sex and gender analysis in applications, in particular in multidisciplinary collaboration</p> <p>Including training in sex and gender analysis as eligible</p>

Dimension	Field of Action	Sub-field of action	Measure
			costs in applications

Annex V: Examples of indicators

Key Area:	Priority	Institution	Goals & Objectives	Related activities	Possible monitoring/ outcome indicators	Source
Human Resources		ULB	<p>-to develop an intentional recruitment strategy to attract more female candidates to STEM academic positions</p> <p>-to increase the number of applications from women for STEM academic positions</p> <p>-to increase the number of women in the academic body of the STEM faculties</p>	Implementation of intentional recruitment strategy for STEM positions (from the academic year 2022-2023)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Share of women and men among applicants - Share of women and men among persons recruited - Success rate for women and men applicants (The success rate is the number of women/ men recruited divided by the total number of women/ men applying for a position. <p>These three indicators should be broken down by:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Scientific field - Academic position - Temporary or permanent position - Part-time or full-time position <p>These indicators can be used to find out if women or men are under-represented among the recruited researchers.</p>	Science Europe: Practical Guide to Improving Gender Equality in Research Organisations https://www.scienceurope.org/media/ubblodu/se_gender_practical-guide.pdf
		IRB Barcelona	Examine the salary situation between men and women holding posts of equal value, according to the remuneration and promotion systems in place	Analyse with a gender perspective the salary situation in the IRB Barcelona	<p>Collect and compare pay data to identify gaps:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -gender distribution by grade/ equal work groups -male and female staff by age and length of service -part time staff by gender by grade <p>Analyse Pay:</p> <p>Calculate average basic pay, then calculate the difference between average pay and total pay of women and men for each equal work group</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Compare access to and amounts received of each element of pay 	Equality and Human Rights Commission (UK) https://www.equalityhumanrights.com/en/multi-page-guide/equal-pay-audit-step-3-collecting-pay-data

Institutional Governance	ECE-NTUA	Support, lead, coordinate and embed gender equality and diversity actions at school level, while co-operating with the established NTUA Gender Equality Committee.	Create a Gender Equality Office	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Budget/ staff dedication -Workload recognition for people who co-ordinate/ participate in the Unit -Number of co-ordinated actions/ measures* -Number of actions/ measures – participate in* -Number of meetings and no. of participants in each meeting* -Number of times requested help/ advice* -Number of website hits* 	PLOTINA Project: https://www.plotina.eu/creation-gender-equality-office-action-2/#1571055341720-dfa9392f-7645
Teaching	UniSalento	Study of the feasibility of establishing specific gender studies courses, through the promotion and participation in gender-related initiatives proposed by faculty and researchers of the University, both training and research	Create gender perspectives in teaching and research, through research initiatives and/or educational proposals for staff and students.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Number of degrees/ post-grad; number of degrees/ post-grad with gender module; (obligatory/ optional) -Number of teaching/ research activities developed to integrate the gender dimension -Number of research projects/ publications that integrate the gender dimension 	Gender-NET https://eige.europa.eu/sites/default/files/d3.11_manuals_with_guidelines_on_the_integration_of_sex_and_gender_analysis_into_research.pdf
Students	FER UoZ	Promotional-informational campaign with female role models in STEM aiming at female students	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -identification and engagement of female role models from higher education and research and industry to participate in activities -organization of events aimed at female students 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Number of recruited role models* -Number of events/ activities organized* -Number of role models/ participants at events/ activities organized* 	Own elaboration

Communication	UniSalento	Ensuring information on actions, tools and services related to gender policies and equal opportunities and promoting their use and dissemination	Create and update on the University website a webpage dedicated to the activities of the Delegate for Equal Opportunities with documents, regulations, news on initiatives and actions in progress related to gender policies (Gender Balance and other relevant studies and analyses)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Creation of webpage (yes/ no)* - Number of updates per year* - Number of downloads of key documents* - Number of (external/ internal) links to webpage* 	Own elaboration
Research	MTF- STU	Increasing awareness of gender equality by raising the number of theses (bachelor's degrees, diploma, dissertations) with the gender equality topic.	Integration of the gender dimension in final theses (bachelor's degrees, diploma, dissertations).	-Number of published final theses (bachelors' theses, diploma theses, dissertations) with gender equality issues, number of solved final theses on the topic of gender equality.	Plotina: https://www.plotina.eu/recognition-dissertations-gender-dimension-into-account-unibo/#1571055341720-dfa9392f-7645
Discrimination & Sexual Harassment	UEFISCDI	Raising awareness about sexual harassment and help identify types of harassment and clearly explain the concept	Informative kit regarding sexual harassment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Number of downloads of kit* -Number of inquiries* -Number of training/ awareness raising events* -Number of participants at training/ awareness raising events* - Number of pre-test/ post-test evaluations with greater awareness of types of sexual harassment* 	EIGE: https://eige.europa.eu/sites/default/files/science_guidelines_on_dealing_with_sexual_harassment_2.pdf
	YU	Establishment of Gender Based Discrimination, Violence and Sexual	Gender Based Discrimination, Violence and Sexual Harassment Prevention Unit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Budget/ staff dedication -Workload recognition for people who co-ordinate/ participate in the Unit 	Own Elaboration

		Harassment Prevention Unit		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Number of co-ordinated actions/ measures/ trainings* -Number of actions/ measures – participate in* -Number of meetings and no. of participants in each meeting* -Number of times requested help/ advice* -Number of website hits* 	
Intersectionality	SRNSFG	Ensure that data collection does not overlook the experiences of individuals with intersectional identities and ensure inclusive and transparent system of data collection.	Gather disaggregated data by gender in conjunction with ethnicity, gender identity, age, disability, religion, etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Information systems incorporate data disaggregated by gender/ ethnicity/ gender identity, age, disability, religion etc. (yes/No)* -Analysis of career progression according to disaggregated data* -Actions/ measures developed on the basis of analysis (yes/ no) * 	Own Elaboration

*indicators own elaboration

